

December 2025

SAPEA Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence in Emergency and Crisis Management

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Artificial Intelligence in Emergency and Crisis Management

SAPEA Literature Review

December 2025

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Summary

This introductory narrative review has been conducted by the SAPEA literature review team at Cardiff University, at the request of the European Commission's SAM Secretariat and on behalf of the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) at DG ECHO. It synthesises recently published evidence on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Disaster Risk Management (DRM). The review addresses questions outlined in the Project Concept Note¹ which focus on opportunities, risks, ethical considerations, as well as alignment with EU legislation and guidelines. It summarises recent review papers in the academic literature, together with published reports and papers by organisations in the field. It is designed to complement the SAPEA Rapid Evidence Review Report (2025), *The role and use of artificial intelligence for emergency and crisis management*.

The narrative review examines the relevant literature within the context of crisis and emergency management. As requested, it seeks to: (1) identify current practices and tools that employ AI in emergency preparedness and operational settings; (2) evaluates what is working, emerging, or problematic; and (3) identifies evidence gaps and areas for future research and investment. It includes general policy-oriented recommendations on the responsible use of AI in disaster preparedness and response, taken from the literature.

Findings of the narrative review include:

Opportunities

A number of opportunities are identified in the literature, which include:

- *Modelling, prediction, forecasting, early-warning.* AI can enhance model accuracy, making forecasting and prediction more efficient, faster and possibly less costly.
- *Crisis monitoring and relief.* AI can enable more effective real-time crisis monitoring and assistance. AI can help with crisis communications.
- *Global assistance.* AI can assist in those parts of the world that lack infrastructure or capacities.

Risks and challenges

A range of risks and challenges are flagged, based on the literature, which include:

- *Data quality and availability.* Incomplete and unrepresentative data, which may lead to inaccurate results and potentially harmful outcomes.
- *Opacity, explainability and transparency.* 'Black box' models can act as a barrier to transparency and accountability.
- *Infrastructure and network resilience issues.*

1 Draft of May 2025, unpublished

Summary

Ethical concerns

- Ethical concerns raised in the literature include concentration of power, dependencies, data and algorithmic bias, potential discrimination, risks to human rights and privacy.

Mitigation of risks

- Possible mitigation strategies suggested in the literature include effective system design that incorporates safeguards, human responsibility and accountability; data quality assurance and traceability; ethical oversight, governance, protection of rights, and legal compliance; network resilience; digital literacy and workforce training.
- The review includes a number of published frameworks and guidelines, all mentioned in the literature.

Existing practices and tools

- The review describes a range of published examples and case studies. Where evidence exists, the effective use of AI is indicated. It includes enhanced sifting and classifying of information; precision and speed of analysis; real-time situation monitoring; and humanitarian support to affected communities.
- Challenges mentioned include the quality, availability and granularity of datasets; lack of data harmonisation and interoperability; problems of generalisability between one crisis situation and another; resource constraints, and risks to the ongoing sustainability of initiatives.

What works, what is problematic, what is emerging

- AI can be effective at predicting certain types of events or situations. It can be a very useful 'research assistant'. Examples of what is problematic include data availability and gaps; the analysis of complex text and data that involves nuance and understanding of context; issues of end-user capability and training; risks of new technological dependencies and growing 'techno-solutionism'; and possible impacts of geopolitical tensions. The review mentions emerging trends like agentic AI and greater personalisation.

Areas for future enquiry

- Areas identified in the literature include matching system requirements against actual data availability and system capabilities; greater consideration of skills and training; incentivising data sharing; examining new technologies and trends; and real-world performance evaluation.

General recommendations for policy

- General recommendations for policy mentioned in the literature include encouraging greater understanding of AI within the policymaking community; support for data creation and sharing; more investment in digital literacy and training; development of ethical AI; ongoing strengthening of infrastructure resilience; enhanced collaboration with stakeholders, including end-users and local communities.

Table of abbreviations and acronyms

AA	Anticipatory action
ADM+S	Automated Decision-Making and Society
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDR	Artificial Intelligence for Digital Response
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application programming interface
CBRN	Chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear
CDI	Combined Drought Indicator
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DAI	Disaster artificial intelligence
DEEP	Data Entry and Exploration Platform
DL	Deep Learning
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EWS	Early warning system
FLP	Facility location problem
GAO	Government Accountability Office
GeoAI	Geospatial artificial intelligence
GIS	Geographic information system
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
ICT	Information and communication technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IoD	Internet of drones
IoT	Internet of things
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LLM	Large language model
ML	Machine Learning
NMHS	National Meteorological and Hydrological Service
NLP	Natural Language Processing
QA	Quality assurance
QC	Quality control
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
RGB	Red-Green-Blue
PIR	Passive infrared
SAR	Search and rescue
SDO	Standards developing organisation
SHIPS	Statistical Hurricane Intensity Prediction Scheme
TEC	Technology Executive Committee

UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
USV	Unmanned surface vehicle
VRP	Vehicle routing problem
WFP	World Food Programme
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
XAI	Explainable artificial intelligence
YOLO	You Only Look Once
4IR	Fourth Industrial Revolution

Context

This narrative review of recent literature was conducted by the SAPEA literature review team at Cardiff University, at the request of the SAM Unit and on behalf of the ERCC in DG ECHO. It aims to address the following scoping questions set out in a Project Concept Note (draft) of May 2025:

- What are the opportunities, risks and ethical issues involved in the use of AI for Disaster Risk Management?
- How can these risks be mitigated, and alignment with [European] Commission guidelines on AI use be ensured?

The Concept Note identified a number of project objectives, which have been covered in the review:

- Identification of existing practices and tools using AI in emergency preparedness and anticipation
- Identification of existing and emerging cases of AI being used in operational situations
- Exploration of what works, what is emerging, and what is uncertain or problematic
- Identification of key gaps in evidence and opportunities for future inquiry or investment
- General recommendations about the use of AI in disaster preparedness and response.

This review is designed to complement the SAPEA Rapid Evidence Review Report, *The role and use of artificial intelligence for emergency and crisis management* (SAPEA, 2025). It is not a systematic review of all available literature but rather an introduction to the topic, covering a broad range of sources. It includes recent reviews in the academic literature and reports by major organisations in the field. The literature described relates to the context of crisis, emergency and disaster risk management. The methods used for the literature review, along with a record of database searches, are available in the Annex.

Introduction

In 1950, Alan Turing asked whether machines could think, and proposed the now-famous Turing test or imitation game.² In 1956, Professor John McCarthy introduced the term ‘artificial intelligence’. In 1959, the first AI laboratory was established at MIT; it took the first steps in Natural Language Processing (NLP). A paper by Artur Samuel in 1959 introduced the term “machine learning” (ML). Publications on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) date from 1979 (Koltsakis, Klontzas & Karantanas, 2023).

In 2019, the European Union High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence defined AI technologies as *‘software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal’* (cited in Bohland, Rechkemmer & Rogers, 2024).

Readers should refer to the SAPEA Rapid Evidence Review Report (2025), which includes definitions of key terms in AI for emergency and crisis management, alongside definitions for crisis and emergency. As noted there, terms are used flexibly, including in this narrative review, depending on how they are described in the literature.

Describing different types of AI

Most current AI systems are classed as ‘narrow’, i.e. they perform specific tasks within a defined set of boundaries. Examples within a disaster setting include prediction, analysis, training, monitoring, communications, routing, and environment sensing. By contrast, ‘general AI’ can work with more complex data environments across different problem sets, within areas of application that have no boundaries. In future, general AI could allow the flexibility and scope of thinking associated with human problem-solving. Within risk and disaster management, it could select certain tasks and connect them together to provide solutions. Currently, however, there are constraints around general AI, which include data, computation, ethics, and practical considerations (Bohland et al., 2024).

Machine learning (ML) finds patterns within data, so is useful for tasks like sensing, data curation and analysis, prediction, and resource optimisation (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). Many traditional models for natural hazard modelling have algorithms designed and coded to represent mathematically the physical laws of nature. By contrast, ML produces outputs based on patterns and statistical relationships within the training data, rather than on physical laws programmed into the model. Some of these patterns in ML may also reflect physical laws because they use data that represents real-world natural hazard events. There are also ‘hybrid’ models that use both programmed physical laws and ML (US

² The participants would be two humans (an interrogator and a contestant) and a machine. The interrogator asks single blinded questions to the other two, and he/she would have to understand which answers come from the contestant and which from the machine (Koltsakis et al., 2023).

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GAO, 2023). ML has a range of uses, from making minor modifications to traditional models (such as assimilating data into a physics-based algorithm) to replacing a traditional model entirely (US GAO, 2023).

Some ML systems are trained under human supervision, using training datasets tagged with descriptors by a supervisor; this then builds a predictive algorithm that can identify and classify untagged data. Unsupervised methods rely on machine networks that analyse data to identify the underlying logic or information structure. Deep learning (DL) is an example of an unsupervised approach, which uses complex neural networks to analyse diverse forms of untagged data. As DL systems adapt in line with advances in data sensors and surveillance tools, this form of architecture may be superior to earlier forms of Disaster AI (DAI). DAIs require appropriate training data —both in quantity and quality— and a set of policies (rules or protocols) to apply learning to a complex disaster situation (Bohland et al., 2024). An NLP tool like ChatGPT is based on a DL model that can analyse data from multiple sources, including past disasters, social media, environmental conditions, and satellite imagery (ESCAP, 2023).

A report by OCHA (2021) notes that AI can be integrated with other technologies, such as mobile applications and chatbots, crisis maps and dashboards, biometric systems, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and the internet of things (IoT), to improve data analysis and decision-making. Crisis maps and dashboards collect, analyse, and display key data during a crisis; they use data from scraping the web, crowdsourcing, remote sensing, satellite imagery analysis, geographic information systems (GIS), data analytics, and/or AI systems (OCHA, 2021).

The potential of AI in disaster and crisis management

Technologies like AI can change humanitarian assistance from one of reaction to anticipation, enabling a faster and earlier response. These technologies can support needs analysis, making the process more people-centred, and enabling more systematic monitoring and evaluation. Such advances could extend humanitarian capacities, protecting more people affected by crises (OCHA, 2021).

As AI demonstrates its potential across a range of natural, technological, and human risk situations, its use is increasing and spreading. Bohland et al. (2024) attribute the expansion of 'disaster AI systems (DAIs)' to: (1) improvements in the architecture and training of AI, making it applicable across different contexts; (2) advances in sensor and surveillance technology, coupled with data storage and processing, which increase the quantity and variety of digital data; (3) growing support from disaster risk reduction (DRR) and emergency response professionals for the deployment of AI; (4) a higher frequency and intensity of major episodic hazards and disasters; and (5) increasing concern about long-term threats brought about by climate change, wars, failing states, poverty, forced migration, and epidemics (Bohland et al., 2024).

An essay for the Harvard Kennedy School Belfer Center examines how multimodal AI could support a crisis response during the different phases of the disaster cycle:

Tools for **prevention** could include the following:

- *Data collection and processing.* AI could be used for continuous data collection and quality control.
- *Event prediction.* Data from a multitude of sources, including sensors, satellite imagery, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and weather stations could be used to assess, monitor, and predict crises.
- *Scenario simulations.* AI could create and then analyse scenarios to assess crisis probabilities and impacts across a range of severities, undertake risk assessments, and help in preparing response strategies.
- *Results interpretation and action planning.* AI could identify the most vulnerable areas in a crisis, develop appropriate response plans, and highlight potential mitigations.

Tools for **pre-disaster action** could include the following:

- *Predictive modelling.* AI could be used to predict potential outcomes of future crises.
- *Public warning systems.* AI could offer citizens next steps.

Tools for **coaching and training** could include the following:

- *Virtual simulations and role-playing.* Emergency managers could be trained using virtual reality (VR) simulations, powered by AI to create immersive experiences. This technology could allow decision-makers to experience crises in the most realistic possible settings.
- *Personalised learning, feedback, and coaching.* AI could provide a training platform that adjusts content, feedback, and suggestions based on the performance and progress of the trainees.

Tools for **safeguarding** could include the following:

- *Evacuation planning.* AI tools could help in determining the fastest and optimal evacuation routes for different areas.
- *Identifying and supporting vulnerable populations.* AI could highlight communities at higher risk, tailoring evacuation interventions and alerts so they get the help they need.
- *Resource allocation.* AI could help determine where to send equipment and supplies before a disaster hits, directing local communities on how to access these resources.
- *Communication and query resolution.* Chatbots could be deployed to address frequently asked questions (FAQs) on evacuation routes and means, shelter and backup facilities, and emergency procedures. Chatbots could also provide personalised guidance and support to community workers and residents.

Tools for **decision support** could include the following:

- *Communication and information dissemination.* AI tools could disseminate critical information and guidance more rapidly, reaching a larger audience in multiple languages.

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- *Emergency response risk assessment and optimisation.* Scenario analysis combined with real-time data analysis could help responders understand the scope of a crisis, identify the risks of various responses, allocate resources, and streamline relief efforts.
- *Rescue and recovery operations.* AI could point responders to survivor locations and identify where to concentrate resources for rescue and recovery operations.

Tools for **real-time data visualisation** could include the following:

- *Decision dashboards.* AI could indicate which decisions are the most urgent, prioritising where humans should be 'in the loop', while also recommending actions to accelerate the crisis response.
- *Risk and response heatmaps.* AI could produce maps to highlight where emergency response is needed and where future response may be required, to direct personnel to the most urgent needs.

Tools for **sentiment analysis** could include the following:

- *Social media monitoring.* AI could synthesise the early signs of crises such as public unrest, protests, disease outbreak, and security threats.
- *Sentiment analysis.* AI could use NLP techniques to analyse text and gauge public sentiment during a crisis.
- *Public opinion polling and surveys.* AI could design and help implement public opinion polls and surveys to collect data on public sentiment during a crisis.
- *Issue tracking and media monitoring.* AI could monitor how the crisis is being portrayed to the public, including the tone and narrative being used about the crisis. This could help determine when and how to counter misinformation.

Tools for **supporting aid** to the community could include the following:

- *Resource management and allocation.* AI could analyse community needs and optimise resource allocation. It could consider factors such as population density, economic needs, along with delivery of critical health and human services.
- *Predictive analysis for specific populations.* AI could synthesise data to identify specific populations that might have extra or specific needs.

Tools for **postcrisis analysis** could include the following:

- *Performance evaluation and impact assessment.* AI could assess the performance of response strategies and evaluate their effectiveness.
- *Evaluate strategies and processes.* AI could assess risks and vulnerabilities brought about by the crisis, helping to develop mitigation strategies.
- *Support transparency.* AI could disclose information that helps members of the public assess the efficacy of the crisis response.
- *Policy and procedure refinement.* AI could inform adjustments to existing policies or procedures (Ellencweig, Lamb, Spaner & Mysore, 2024).

Humanitarian predictive analytics harness 'big data' so that ML and statistical models can calculate the likely characteristics of emergencies. This makes it possible to predict where and when disasters could happen, what the defining characteristics of the situation could be, and who would be the most affected populations. A literature review found a series of claims for the role of predictive analytics, including: (1) mitigation, informing mitigation phase strategies; (2) preparedness, providing early warning to authorities, citizens, and humanitarian actors about imminent threats; (3) response, helping provide situational awareness. The review noted that at that time, relatively little work had been done on how predictive analytics could be used during recovery efforts (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

Opportunities, risks and ethics

Opportunities

Modelling, prediction, forecasting, early warning

Modelling. The US Government Accountability Office (US GAO, 2023) reviewed how ML was being used to model natural hazards. It interviewed a range of stakeholder groups, convened a meeting of experts with the National Academies, and reviewed key reports and scientific literature. The GAO found that ML was being used in some forecasting models. A few ML models were in operation for routine forecasting; some were considered close to operational, while others required a long period of development and testing. The GAO identified potential benefits of applying ML in modelling, including:

1. Reducing the time needed to make forecasts, by replacing parts of models that are slow and/or increase the cost of modelling
2. Increasing model accuracy, by using data that traditional models cannot use, and by creating 'synthetic data' (see below for details) to fill gaps
3. Reducing the uncertainty of models' output by improving ensemble modelling (US GAO, 2023).

Ensemble modelling can reduce the uncertainty in model predictions by using multiple models (rather than just one) and combining their predictions. For example, ML could create ensembles using hundreds of models; this could produce more reliable forecasts. On the other hand, the ML techniques used for large ensemble models are more complex, are harder to train, and potentially more challenging to understand and troubleshoot than other ML methods (US GAO, 2023).

In weather forecasting, some evaluations have shown that AI/ML models surpass physics-based models in predicting certain weather variables and extreme or hazardous events, such as tropical cyclones. For example, on longer timescales, studies have shown that AI/ML models can predict the El Niño Southern Oscillation up to three years ahead (cited in WMO, 2024), although some evaluations of these AI models have found limitations in their performance.

ML has the potential to reduce uncertainty in some situations where data do not exist or are insufficient, by creating synthetic data based on prior information. At the same time, this method would require appropriate expertise of the simulated hazards, extensive training of the ML algorithm, and further investigation to confirm that the algorithm is generalisable to other geographic areas (US GAO, 2023).

Efficiency, speed and cost. A report by the Stockholm Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) looked at the potential of AI to address climate-related security risks, based on desk research and expert interviews (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). The report suggests that AI can make early warning and long-term climate hazard modelling more efficient. ML can speed up and reduce the costs of collecting data; algorithms

can then detect environmental changes, integrating and finding linkages between data from various sources (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). ML can also speed up data assimilation, updating models by integrating current environmental observations. Quicker assimilation allows models to use more data, providing a more accurate picture of conditions and resulting in a forecast that is more precise and faster (US GAO, 2023). ML could speed up quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) processes (US GAO, 2023). AI/ML models can also reduce the computational costs of producing datasets. For example, AI/ML methods can be used for weather prediction, where previously such capabilities were limited to large global forecasting centres; now, they can be accessed by national meteorological and hydrological services that previously did not have sufficient resources. Lowering costs has also encouraged smaller public and private entities to enter the field (WMO, 2024).

Anticipation, preparedness, planning and early warning systems (EWS). ML can enable designers to create models that are more complex, using larger and more heterogeneous datasets. AI can make EWS impact assessment more comprehensive, by integrating socio-economic as well as environmental data (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). Information processing using AI can also help strengthen urban infrastructure and planning, guiding decision-makers to prioritise adaptation measures and allocate resources (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). A policy insight paper by the Humanitarian Forecast Working Group (CEPR, 2024) looks at automated prediction systems for humanitarian anticipatory action (AA), planning and intervening ahead of new crises or the deepening of existing crises. The rapid progress in ML data availability has made forecasts much more accurate.

Support to the Global South and other vulnerable countries. AI can help with sensing and data collection for EWS in countries that lack the necessary infrastructure and capacity for traditional climate information systems. Using satellite images can be both safer and cheaper than installing and maintaining facilities in conflict and other fragile zones (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). AI can address the lack of climate-related data in these areas, including the use of remote sensing systems, satellite imagery, and social media (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Serious security threats. AI could enhance detection, surveillance, and response capabilities for CBRN (chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear) threats, optimising response strategies (Ajaykumar, 2024).

Crisis monitoring and relief

In climate-related disasters, the SIPRI report (Kim & Boulanin, 2023) suggests that AI could be used for near real-time crisis monitoring, enabling relief workers to navigate, find resources and reach people in need. Aerial imagery (UAVs, drones) could be used to monitor the disaster and identify damage to local infrastructure. UAVs could be helpful in places where communications infrastructure is limited and when non-intrusive monitoring is required. AI could assist the mapping of affected regions, risk assessment, identifying populations in need, and for disaster communication. AI could enable the use of autonomous robots and UAVs for humanitarian aid delivery during climate-related disasters. AI may also support decision-making during disaster responses by providing real-time information (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

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Psychological impacts, public consultation, communication. The social and behavioural sciences can offer insight during a crisis. A rapid review by the Institute of Development Studies cites deeper understanding of cultural, social, political, behavioural, psychological, and economic issues, amongst others (Grant, 2024). LLMs can facilitate stakeholder and public consultations (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). AI can help contextualise and communicate complex information for decision-making (WMO, 2024). Social media can be a useful data source; AI could support real-time monitoring that could detect trends and sense public opinion. ML could develop the capacity to capture nuances in languages. One the other hand, one of the challenges of using AI, and specifically NLP approaches, is that social media communication can be difficult for AI to parse due to the informal style of expression, irregular punctuation, the use of abbreviations, and frequently ambiguous descriptions (Xu, Ma, Li, & Cheng, 2025).

Risks

Important potential shortcomings of AI include biases, data availability, and opacity. In disaster and crisis situations, data are often incomplete or unavailable. The risk of biases in data or algorithms can have negative impacts on both systems and people. AI may make errors in cases or events that fall outside historical patterns and are not included in training or observed data (so-called 'black swans'). The full extent and impact of AI as a risk factor is not yet fully understood, so it requires both careful and continuous assessment (Kameraj et al., 2024).

According to a systematic review by Farazmehr and Wu (2023), many AI-enabled approaches to disaster management rely on statistical data analytics, social media, and GIS-based methods, and these have potential pitfalls. Firstly, using data from previous disasters may not necessarily lead to accurate predictions about future ones, due to each disaster's unique features. Secondly, social media is not always truthful so there are limitations to its usefulness; moreover, people may not have access to telecommunication networks to provide updates. Thirdly, although GIS can provide comprehensive data, the volume and complexity of such data create challenges for storage and analysis (Farazmehr & Wu, 2023). Other limitations of using AI systems in disaster management include high computational demands and the machine's lack of empathy and transparency (Farazmehr & Wu, 2023).

Themes identified by Diehr, Ogunyiola and Dada (2025) concern data quality and accuracy; model interpretability and reliability; privacy and security challenges; ethical and social concerns; and dependence on high-quality data. There can be issues with generalisability; for example, models trained on data from a particular region may not be generalisable to other regions. Similarly, the 'black box' nature of many advanced models can be a barrier to using them in real-life scenarios; if human decision-makers do not understand how a model arrived at conclusions, it may lead to errors and poor decisions (Diehr et al., 2025).

The collection and processing of high-resolution satellite imagery and location information raise concerns about privacy, as data can reveal sensitive personal information (Diehr et al., 2025). Extracting

large amounts of data from social media is also fraught with ethical concerns regarding privacy. Some literature points to risks around the potential misuse of geospatial data that could be manipulated and used for malicious purposes, such as spreading misinformation and propaganda (Diehr et al., 2025).

Diehr et al. (2025) warn that over-relying on AI and ML technologies can result in neglecting human knowledge and judgment, and that biases in models may disproportionately affect vulnerable populations. The authors suggest that the involvement of domain experts, policymakers, and stakeholders is necessary to address challenges, ensure the responsible use of emerging technologies and build trust in them.

Some of these risks and challenges are described in further detail below:

Modelling. The GAO identified challenges to the development and use of ML models. These include: (1) limitations and shortages in data; (2) lack of trust and understanding of the algorithms and concerns about bias; (3) limited collaboration between stakeholders, such as researchers and forecasters, posing challenges for model development; (4) gaps in workforce and resources; (5) high upfront costs to develop ML models (US GAO, 2023).

General vs specialised models. Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) argue that developing general models is difficult because it requires a large and comprehensive training dataset that accounts for different conditions, scenarios, and environments, with the size and complexity of the resulting model demanding significant computational time and power. On the other hand, specialised models made for specific types of disasters and environment can provide accuracy without such high resource demands (Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi, 2024).

Data biases. If training data are not representative of reality, then the system may fail at the task and perpetuate or create new biases. If the dataset does not reflect variations over time or is inconsistent or too specific to a particular geographical context, then the value of the system's predictions may be limited (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). Data that is outdated or unrepresentative can lead to inaccurate and potentially discriminatory outcomes. ML models can also contain errors, due to existing errors within traditional models. As ML models can be difficult to make generalisable, their performance may vary according to location (US GAO, 2023).

Data availability and data sharing. Where data are unavailable, limited, or of poor quality, AI cannot generate helpful predictions, and those predictions may even be harmful. The representativeness of the training dataset depends on data availability. For data on climate-related security risks, for example, it can be hard to find accurate and representative datasets. Many countries lack a proper network of ground meteorological and hydrological stations, particularly in conflict-affected and fragile countries. Remote sensing technology could help address the shortage of measurement stations, but not every country is able to make use of this technology. Certain countries may be unwilling to share data collected by their own agencies (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). The need for large datasets is particularly complicated when it comes to less common languages, and especially those languages with small speaker communities or that exist purely in oral form (Rocca, Tamagnone, Fekih, Contla, & Rekabsaz,

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2023). There are community-driven efforts to develop datasets and models for languages that have limited resources, such as the Masakhané³ initiative, whose aim is to promote resources and model development for African languages, and the Gamayun project, aimed at crowdsourcing resources for machine translation for humanitarian applications (Rocca et al., 2023).

Data challenges include gaps in observational data, incompatible data, and difficulty accessing data. Key gaps in observational data include:

1. *Geographic gaps.* Observational infrastructure can often be located where extreme events are expected to happen. This would then limit model usability in areas where natural hazards may not have been historically frequent.
2. *Data availability.* There is a variety of factors that can limit data availability. For example, some systems do not capture certain data; data may be limited for rare natural hazard events, and some ground and satellite data are only obtainable intermittently.
3. *Completeness of historical data.* For effective model performance, access to complete and accurate historical data that represent conditions appropriately is vital.
4. *Private data.* Some data may be unavailable or inaccessible, due to privacy restrictions.
5. *Data compatibility.* In some cases, the necessary data are available for modelling, but are not compatible with organisational standards and/or priorities, or in suitable programming languages, for example: (a) data from certain sources may be unavailable to others; (b) converting programming languages may require additional labour and other resources; (c) to be “AI-ready”, standards are needed for how data are collected, labelled, or used (US GAO, 2023).

Socio-economic and other social science data. Obtaining current and high-quality data on socio-economic indicators, political perceptions, and social grievances can be difficult, resource-intensive and time-consuming, as well as requiring rigorous verification procedures. In such cases, the risk is that policy interventions, based on incomplete and inadequate analysis, may not target the right people and could make a situation worse. Lack of infrastructure may limit people’s ability to engage with social media and other platforms, with the result that certain opinions may be absent or under-represented. This gives rise to necessary caution about relying solely on insights from AI developed from social media data, or by AI-assisted public consultations. The World Bank’s Global Data Facility⁴ is an attempt to tackle data challenges and enhance government information systems (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Opacity, explainability, transparency, trust. As with traditional modelling methods, conveying confidence levels, uncertainties, and the limitations of an AI-supported system in an understandable way are vital for decision-making (WEF, 2024). Decision-makers should be able to understand and evaluate how and why the model produced a certain outcome. Opacity (‘black boxes’) makes it difficult for end users to understand why and how the systems came to specific recommendations. It can also hinder other researchers from replicating and learning from existing models (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

3 <https://www.masakhane.io>

4 <https://worldbank.org/en/programs/global-data-facility>

Trust in black-box models is traditionally based on cross-validation of the model's performance (US GAO, 2023).

Accountability. 'Algorithm aversion' means that humans judge algorithms more harshly on their mistakes, making it harder for algorithms to be part of a decision-making process. Algorithms cannot be held to account, and consequently it is not clear who should be held responsible (Muench, Whyte, Hauer, Maleville, & Asikainen, 2024).

Human skillsets. Gradually, as AI takes over tasks once done by people, human skills can atrophy, leading to deskilling (Drexel & Withers, 2024).

Endogeneity. Decision-makers should be aware of whether a variable they forecast is endogenous to their decisions, as it could lead to bias and flawed decision-making. For example, certain humanitarian needs at a location could be amplified or prevented by the decision-maker, as a result of endogeneity (Muench et al., 2024).

Disinformation. Tools like ChatGPT enable a user with no programming skills to create variations of a disinformation message; this can then be shared with online bots that spread the messages online (Fournier-Tombs, Brubaker & Albrecht, 2023). According to the authors, AI-generated disinformation and the role it plays should be addressed as a priority.

Network resilience. A 2025 paper by the OECD's Working Party on Connectivity Services and Infrastructures (WPCSI) has looked at the resilience of communication networks, focusing on three areas: (1) technical aspects of network resilience; (2) resilience metrics; and (3) providing a framework by which to categorise policies on strengthening resilience. System failures are a leading cause of communication network outages, accounting for 93.5% of lost user hours in EU Member States in 2022, with malicious actions accounting for 3.8% of lost user hours, natural phenomena 1.5%, and human error 1.2% (ENISA, cited by OECD, 2025a).

Other risks. *Other risks associated with threats to civilian safety and/or to society include:*

CBRN threats. Ajaykumar (2024) warns that increased accessibility to information and materials by LLMs can enable CBRN attacks. For example, AI-assisted drones could target vulnerable populations or critical infrastructure. AI could also help automate various stages of an attack. Cyberattacks could target emergency response systems during a CBRN-related incident. An emergency or an act of negligence could result in a leak of CBRN materials. According to the author, regulation and oversight of emerging technologies that could be exploited for CBRN purposes are insufficient (Ajaykumar, 2024).

Increasing AI autonomy. AI systems with control over resources, critical infrastructure and military systems could pose a potential risk, enabling state and non-state actors to deploy lethal autonomous weapons. AI-driven decision-making processes could inadvertently raise geopolitical tensions or fail to identify emerging threats. The 'value misalignment' of AI (when AI systems fail to adequately follow the *'imperfectly conveyed goals of their creators'* (Stauffer et al.,

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2023)) could pose challenges for societal resilience. As systems become increasingly autonomous, AI could introduce unforeseen consequences, making it difficult to predict and manage potential hazards (Stauffer et al., 2023).

AI itself as an existential threat. Some experts see the existential risk from AI itself as a pressing priority, whereas others dismiss this. Drexel and Withers (2024) suggest that the speed of AI's deployment, the diversity of potential applications, and its growing capabilities may increase catastrophic risks in a variety of fields.

Ethical issues

Ethical concerns include power imbalances, potential discrimination, human rights and privacy, as well as accountability arising from inaccurate predictions and technical faults (Kim & Boulanin, 2023; Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi, 2024). According to the recent report by the International Panel on the Information Environment (IPIE, 2025), *'AI remains fundamentally a dual-use technology. The same systems that can help predict conflict hotspots, facilitate dialogue and process humanitarian data can efficiently spread misinformation, amplify division, and deepen societal polarization. The technology's substantial energy requirements and surveillance applications present additional concerns.'*

Equity and concentration of power. There are ethical concerns around who develops AI technology, and who is affected by its design and use (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). The resources to develop ML systems are in the hands of the few countries and companies that have capacity like computing power, data, and expertise. Countries most severely exposed to risks like climate change are in the Global South and often lack financial, technical, and human resources to develop their own AI systems. Consequently, they often find themselves relying on external agents such as international organisations, foreign donors, research institutions, and companies (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). People directly affected by crises may not be able to influence the development of AI systems, whereas private companies and decision-makers with the means to do so may not have sufficient contextual understanding to design AI solutions for specific needs and situations (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Between November 2023 and April 2024, RAND Europe, in partnership with Athena Infonomics and [glass.ai](#), explored current practices in the use of emerging technologies in the humanitarian sector. Workshop participants saw increasing risks of 'digital extractivism' (defined as *'a form of exploitation based on the virtualisation or digitisation of commodities and services through a borderless digital capitalism that perpetuates pre-existing colonial practices of value grabbing and wealth accumulation'* (Paillé et al., 2024)); power asymmetries resulting from overreliance on technologies controlled by private companies; and safety and security risks stemming from faster adoption over the next decade. This highlights potential challenges relating to a lack of transparency around humanitarian–private sector partnerships, and the subsequent undermining of the *'humanitarian neutrality'* principle. It has led some humanitarian researchers and institutions to call for a new research and practice agenda

around *'cyber humanitarian interventions'* that proactively seek to prevent and mitigate these risks (Paillé et al., 2024).

A literature review on the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) found that African countries are held back from realising the full potential of technologies by a lack of skills, infrastructure, stakeholder involvement, and relevant policies. The gaps and challenges cluster around ethics, security, and inequality (Signe, n.d.).

Rocca et al. (2023) noted that NLP is rarely implemented in the humanitarian sector beyond pilot projects. When it is deployed, it is often commercial tools and third-party services that are not evaluated or customised for specific applications; such tools can lack the necessary transparency and control. Again, concerns about the need for large amounts of relevant training data, and ethics connected to the deployment of technologies are raised (Rocca et al., 2023).

Dependencies and representation. The need for computing power and data science expertise makes it challenging for small and local players to lead on predictive analytics, potentially creating new dependencies. This may lead to a form of *'digital humanitarianism'* that *'reflects, reproduces, and amplifies patterns of historic inequality including gender, race, and class'* (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020). The low representation of marginalised people in datasets is partly due to their relative exclusion from digital connectivity, ownership, and use. Overreliance on predictive analytics may lead to the neglect of issues that are important but less predictable, and the silencing of people whose experiences are not represented in historical data or whose views are not present on social media (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020). This runs the risk of reproducing past errors, prejudices, and inequalities (Kamberaj, Aebi, Hauri, & Gajos, 2024).

Discrimination and impacts of bias. Jain, Dhupper, Shrivastava, Kumar, and Kumari (2023) warn that algorithms with in-built biases may be used for decisions about how distribute resources or organise evacuation efforts, resulting in issues with justice and equality. Forms of bias include: (1) technical bias, which can affect the AI's algorithmic process through design choices; (2) interpretive bias, from the implicit cognitive biases of individuals or groups who develop or use AI systems; and (3) organisational bias, from the procedures and practices of institutions that develop and/or use ML systems. Organisations that use ML without sufficiently robust procedures may deploy systems that are inaccurate or unreliable (US GAO, 2023).

Privacy and data misuse. External third parties may access and use data for non-humanitarian purposes, leading to surveillance, discrimination or persecution, and compromising the principled delivery of humanitarian assistance (OCHA, 2021).

Consequential impacts of forecasts. Forecasts may be self-fulfilling or self-defeating. For example, a consequence of predicting armed conflict could be that foreign investors withdraw investment or close borders. This raises ethical concerns about who should have access to a given forecast. A decision-maker who becomes very good at mitigating risk could impact on training data's ability to predict future events unless all scenarios are considered (Muench et al., 2024).

Risk mitigation and alignment

De-humanisation. Automating algorithmic processes may be dehumanising and potentially in conflict with humanitarian commitments to human-centred and participatory processes (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020). As AI takes an increasing role in content generation and interaction, human agency reduces. Digital spaces may become environments where algorithms primarily engage with other algorithms, which then impacts on human connection and pro-social interaction. On the other hand, pro-social or harm mitigation tools may have an artificial bias toward superficial positivity. These systems might suppress productive tension or disagreement (IPIE, 2025).

Risk mitigation and alignment

Digital tools may not necessarily lead to better decisions, especially in the humanitarian sector. A 'back to basics' approach could identify problems based on user need, with solutions located along a spectrum from 'no-tech' to 'high-tech'. Decisions would be linked to a clear problem statement at every stage of design, development and deployment of AI, with effective leadership to ensure transparency and direction, both strategically and operationally. A 'digital humanitarian space' could safeguard the digital rights and protections of people affected by crises (OCHA, 2021).

In the EU, the 2016 GDPR and the AI Act seek to ensure the integrity of individuals' data that is processed by AI systems (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). The EU AI Act states that high-risk AI systems must be transparent about their operation and data usage (CEPR, 2024). The regulation emphasises human oversight to ensure decisions are not completely automated, and it incorporates ethical principles like respect for human dignity, non-discrimination, and fairness (CEPR, 2024).

Both private and public organisations have developed guidance on incorporating ethical principles such as fairness, accountability, transparency, and safety for ML use (Muench et al., 2024). Additional measures may include establishing ethical review procedures and technology impact assessments (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

International support. Conflict-affected and other fragile countries may need support from external organisations and partners in the Global North for additional technical and financial resources (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

A report by the Harvard Kennedy School (Ellencweig et al., 2024) highlights the following risks and possible mitigations:

- 1. Potential for bias.** Designing systems with safeguards against biased outcomes, inaccurate predictions, and false alarms.
- 2. Privacy.** Ensuring data collection addresses privacy concerns, the disclosure of personally identifiable information, or historic discrimination.

- 3. Decisions with significant market and other impacts.** Where AI predicts a possible crisis, subsequent decisions may have vital consequences. Models need to clarify the level of certainty in their analysis and validate predictions.
- 4. Data accuracy and combating misinformation.** Data need to be tailored enough to represent possible disaster scenarios of the given location, including factors like geography, history, changing weather patterns, and population dynamics. It is important to verify data reliability and address potential risks of AI-generated content. Specific guardrails around mission-critical tools, as well as transparency about their use, can help.
- 5. Ethical oversight and legal compliance.** Prioritising protection of individual rights, privacy, and data security, and avoiding any potential misuse of personal information.
- 6. Human collaboration, engagement, and governance.** Designing AI systems that ensure human responsibility and accountability, as far as possible.
- 7. Traceability, sourcing, and transparency.** Being able to track, understand, and explain the origins of generative AI algorithms and models; improving transparency by allowing public access to AI data and details of operations.
- 8. Continual assessment and improvement.** Establishing mechanisms for assessment and improvement of AI-driven simulations and programs.
- 9. Safety protocols and contingency plans.** Providing robust safety protocols and contingency plans to address unforeseen issues or challenges that may arise during AI-driven simulations.
- 10. Community engagement and public trust.** Involving the community in the development and implementation of AI-driven disaster preparedness strategies (Ellencweig et al., 2024).

Some of these aspects are explored further in the literature:

Data and algorithm quality. The AI system should be trained on reliable and representative data (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). Jain et al. (2023) recommend establishing standards for data collection and analysis, continuously evaluating algorithms to identify and remedy biases. The authors suggest that community stakeholders be engaged in the design and implementation of algorithms to ensure they represent the needs and priorities of different communities. Rocca et al. (2023) discuss the need to limit the negative effects of model biases, by improving explainability and by considering the ethics of data collection, sharing, and analysis when using NLP in humanitarian contexts. For example, there may be sensitive information in text data that is difficult to identify and remove automatically, putting vulnerable individuals at risk. The authors suggest this is a barrier to open sourcing in humanitarian contexts, hence a need for efficient text anonymisation (Rocca et al., 2023).

Some ML models have proprietary restrictions and limited information about data sources, hindering transparency, interpretability, and explainability (US GAO, 2023). The SIPRI report (Kim & Boulanin, 2023) mentions that in the context of climate security, biases could be addressed by acquiring more of the appropriate data, adjusting selection criteria for groups that are considered marginalised or under-represented, increasing a model's complexity to account for differences between groups, and taking

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special measures to redress historical biases. SIPRI cautions that each mitigation strategy carries its own risks that need careful handling (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Protection of rights and privacy. The way in which data are gathered, stored, shared, and used should consider data privacy and impacts that could stem from design bias or possible misuse of AI (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). Generative AI systems may retain data to ‘train’ their models, creating possible privacy concerns where data are personally identifiable and/or are sensitive in nature. Datasets such as feedback from affected populations or interviews must be handled with extra care and not be input into publicly available systems (UNICEF, 2024). In the context of SAR, Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) warn that confidentiality must be ensured of data obtained during SAR missions (such as video footage); operators should be trained in privacy and data security.

An approach to data privacy that has been suggested is ‘*Federated Learning*’ (FL), first introduced by Google in 2016, which is a type of ML whereby models can be trained by multiple parties using locally stored data without the need for sharing it, thus preserving data privacy (Belfeki, Krichen, Bouazizi, & Zidi, 2025). A representation of FL for disaster management, as appeared in the article by Belfeki et al. (2025), is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ‘Simple representation of FL for disaster management’ (Belfeki, Krichen, Bouazizi, & Zidi, 2025, p. 650).

Some of the challenges associated with using FL in disaster management contexts are data heterogeneity; computational resources on edge devices (which connect a local to an external network) where the required data are stored; and delays in communication systems (‘communication latency’). Edge devices such as IoT sensors, drones, and smartphones usually have limited computational resources and so lightweight FL systems are needed for use on them. Belfeki et al. (2025) refer to Differential Privacy (DP) methods, which introduce random ‘noise’ into models and improves individual data privacy while resulting in a slight reduction in performance. The authors also refer to

Homomorphic Encryption (HE) methods that allow encrypted computations on local updates, but they increase computational demands on local edge devices.

Responsible development of AI. Professionals involved in the design of AI systems should consider its potential harm and examine risk assessment methodologies on responsible AI innovation (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Trust in AI. Three aspects that can help build trust in ML models include: (1) transparent AI, making information accessible about the data and decisions used to design develop, train, and operate the model, together with information about the model's limitations; (2) interpretable AI, building the model in a way that enables a user to understand its development and output; (3) explainable AI, or methods and techniques that produce accurate, explainable models of why and how an AI algorithm arrives at a specific decision (US GAO, 2023).

Human-computer relationship. Calibration can help ensure that AI systems 'know' when they can act confidently, and when to seek assistance or avoid high-stakes decision-making (Drexel & Withers, 2024). Part of the risk profile for AI within high-risk domains include understanding how AI tools are integrated into broader systems, and how human operators respond to systems in practice. Human-machine teaming is a field of study that examines how the design of automation-enabled systems can work with the cognitive and emotional characteristics of diverse operators (Drexel & Withers, 2024).

Digital literacy. Digital literacy is crucial, as citizens must be equipped to find trusted information, identify misinformation and disinformation, protect their privacy, and understand AI capabilities and limitations (IPIE, 2025).

Open-source models and open data. Advocates argue that open access to AI tools can act as a hedge against AI companies amassing too much power. On the other hand, critics worry that the open release of AI models could pose serious risks. Proponents counter that open-source approaches have helped improve software security and stability; openness may provide incentives to develop comprehensive safety mechanisms. This debate is ongoing (Drexel & Withers, 2024). In any case, data must always be well-documented, including metadata. A lack of discoverability can be helped by providing links to open data on data discovery platforms (WEF, 2024).

Network resilience. Using a mix of suppliers and technologies reduces the risk of simultaneous failures arising from shared vulnerabilities. Technologies like cloud integration, virtualisation, and AI-enhanced network resilience can enable workloads to be relocated seamlessly, as needed. Harmonisation of resilience metrics is important for benchmarking and evidence-based policymaking in emergency communications. Responders are moving more towards mobile broadband and satellite technologies (OECD, 2025a). In the EU, the *Council Recommendation on a Union-wide coordinated approach to strengthen the resilience of critical infrastructure*⁵ invites Member States to make use of potential funding opportunities, including trans-European networks, to enhance the resilience of communications

5 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:JOC_2023_020_R_0001

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networks. The *European Electronic Communications Code*⁶ includes an obligation for Member States to take steps to ensure the availability of voice communication and Internet access provided over communication networks in the case of a catastrophic network breakdown. An EU Directive requires Member States to have a resilience plan or similar for public communication networks and service providers (OECD, 2025a).

Prompt injection. One of the risks of utilising LLMs in crisis management is that they can be vulnerable to prompt injection attacks. These can include malicious prompts, causing the LLM to override its original instructions and perform potentially harmful actions. It can result in data breaches, biased outputs, and other harms (Abdur Rahman et al., 2025) and is a form of ‘black box’ vulnerability (Lan, Kaul, & Jones, 2025). It can be direct, by embedding malicious prompts into the LLM input data, or indirect, by hiding such instructions within external sources like websites, texts, or emails to which the LLM has access (Lan, Kaul, & Jones, 2025). Infection mechanisms develop continuously, so research in this area must be ongoing (Dinu, Danciu, Vintila, & Balan, 2025). A recent review by Nair et al. (2025) summarised some of the current literature on prompt injection.

There is a need for continuous fine-tuning of LLMs to enable them to resist increasingly sophisticated attacks. Being more discerning when it comes input data, research and technological advancements, and community collaboration are needed to counter such threats (Abdur Rahman et al., 2025). Some of the methods described include using a filtering layer, where the LLM’s task is to evaluate the input and either allow or not allow further use of the data (which is similar to spam filtering tasks) (Dinu et al., 2025); prompt injection detectors that can be trained on datasets of known attacks (Jacob, Alzahrani, Hu, Alomair, & Wagner, 2025); building multi-staged defence architectures; integrating security considerations directly into the LLMs’ training; and creating frameworks to increase LLMs’ resistance to prompt attacks by using synthetic datasets (Jain et al., 2025).

Frameworks and guidance

The development of data science is outpacing ethical and practical guidance. A framework developed by the Humanitarian Data Science and Ethics Group⁷ sets out ethical and practical guidelines for humanitarian data (DSEG, 2020). Although humanitarian agencies are publishing their own data protection manuals, there is a lack of cross-organisational and sector-wide guidance.

Harvard’s Berkman Klein Center for Internet and Society analysed the content of 36 documents of AI principles from a variety of sectors. Their analysis found the following eight core themes: 1) privacy, 2) accountability, 3) safety and security, 4) transparency and explainability, 5) fairness and non-discrimination, 6) human control of technology, 7) professional responsibility, 8) promotion of human values (DSEG, 2020).

6 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/european-electronic-communications-code.html>

7 <https://www.hum-dseg.org>

Public-private partnerships are generally regarded as positive, but there are several risks. Communities should not be seen as ‘testbeds’ or ‘test sites’; technologies should never be applied in countries when they would not be permitted elsewhere (such as in EU Member States or the US) (DSEG, 2020).

DSEG (2020) points to a lack of documented evidence around issues like data bias, discrimination, de-anonymisation, and weaponisation. Some work has been performed by the OCHA Centre for Humanitarian Data around data incident management. A Guidance Note by OCHA’s Centre for Humanitarian Data examines how humanitarian ethics can be combined with data ethics. The Guidance Note recommends focusing on the following areas to support ethical data practice: 1) establish clear codes of conduct for ethical data management; 2) support staff to identify, understand, and debate ethical issues using common tools; 3) introduce ‘ethical audits’ as part of standard practice (DSEG, 2020).

The following documents were seen as ‘sector-leading’ on humanitarian data responsibility: (1) the *ICRC Handbook on Data Protection in Humanitarian Response*, (2) the *IOM Data Protection Manual*, (3) UN OCHA, *Data Responsibility Guidelines*. Access Now has compiled a report examining the human rights implications of AI, and the Council of Europe has published recommendations on the human rights impacts of algorithmic systems (DSEG, 2020). Users of predictive analytics should ensure that they remain people-centred and problem-driven, rather than technology-centred and solution-driven (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

Standards. Work is being undertaken by international standards developing organisations (SDOs), including the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), and the International Telecommunication Union (ITU). Other UN agencies, including the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) and World Food Programme (WFP), are also contributing to technical regulations, frameworks, recommended practices and de-facto standards (Kuglitsch et al., 2022). In December 2020, ITU, together with the WMO and UNEP, established the Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence for Natural Disaster Management.⁸ The Focus Group is developing a roadmap, setting out existing standards and technical guidelines from different international, national, and regional SDOs (WEF, 2024).

Data harmonisation is a major concern addressed in the *Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030*.⁹ It is important that databases be accurate, accessible, credible, and reliable. This requires a rigorous data collection methodology and hosting by reputable institutions. As the data used in civil protection is sensitive data, adequate privacy protection procedures must be in place (Kamberaj et al., 2024).

AI safety issues. Government agencies should explore the risks of introducing AI into high-impact domains (Drexel & Withers, 2024). Strategies to enhance robustness include diversification of training data, ensemble systems to improve accuracy, and provision for fallbacks (for example, seeking human

8 <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4ndm/Pages/default.aspx>

9 <https://www.undrr.org/publication/sendai-framework-disaster-risk-reduction-2015-2030>

Current practices and tools

input). There is a fine line between achieving international competitiveness whilst ensuring AI safety; some countries have established AI safety institutes. Ensuring sufficient attention is paid to all AI safety issues will remain a challenge, especially as older generations of ML engineers move on or retire (Drexel & Withers, 2024). A paper from the OECD (2025b) provides a common framework for reporting AI incidents, whilst also giving countries the ability to tailor responses to their domestic policies and legal frameworks. Based on 29 criteria, the framework aims to help policymakers understand AI incidents across diverse contexts, identify those systems at high risk, assess current and emerging risks, and evaluate the impact of AI on people and planet.

Current practices and tools

This section describes a range of examples and case studies, found in the recent published literature.

Uses of AI. Based on evidence from 600 articles on conflict settings and peacebuilding, a summary report for policymakers shows that AI is being used to strengthen early warning and forecasting systems; enable digital dialogue and civic engagement; support crisis mapping and humanitarian response; promote pro-social interaction and mitigate polarisation (IPIE, 2025). A recent report by the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction contains nine use cases from the Americas and Caribbean, including a description of each project, best practices and lessons learned (UNDRR, 2025).

Using LLMs at the European Crisis Management Laboratory. In an 18-month study (January 2023 to July 2024), the use of LLMs was examined as a means to enhance scientific analyses performed by the European Crisis Management Laboratory (Galliano et al., 2024). The focus was on Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques (a way of supplementing static training data with additional new sources) to collect information from specific databases, including some developed at the Joint Research Centre (JRC). The study suggested that automated processing can be applied to large quantities of data, sifting out information that is irrelevant. Although the prototypes had limitations, the overall assessment was positive. Among lessons learned is that there is a need to allow for human expert validation of the AI-extracted information; analysts should be trained to evaluate the quality of AI's results and AI itself could assess the quality of its own output. Going forward, models trained with data for specific tasks should yield better results. Semantic indexing (understanding context and intent) of the information used in RAG should improve the output of the models. Comparing results from different models is helpful for assessing content quality and/or providing more reliable outcomes. A joint study between commercial and open solution partners could assist in improving output quality. The report suggests that it is also an opportunity to use knowledge from historical archives of data and analysis, allowing the identification of trends not necessarily detected from past events, as well as the compilation of databases about human losses and the impact of past disasters.

Advantages of neural networks, decision trees, and random forests

Figure 2. Advantages of neural networks, decision trees, and random forests (Jain et al., 2023, p. 5).

Machine learning algorithms in weather forecasting. Jain et al. (2023) describe different types of ML algorithms that can be used for weather pattern and natural hazard predictions, as shown in Figure 2. Applications of neural networks include analysing data sources such as satellite images, atmospheric data, and historical weather data to identify patterns and make weather predictions. Decision trees are based on a set of ‘if-then’ rules and can be used to analyse data such as humidity, temperature, and precipitation. Random forests are a collection of decision trees, each trained on a subset of the available data, with each tree’s prediction used for the final prediction made by the random forest; such algorithms can be used to analyse complex interactions between variables. ML algorithms can improve the precision and speed of natural hazard predictions, reducing the impact of disasters by facilitating EWS and pre-emptive actions. There are many types of data sources algorithms can use, which are summarised in Figure 3, as appeared in Jain et al. (2023). They also point out that ML algorithms require huge amounts of data to make accurate predictions and to design, operate, and maintain such systems, qualified personnel are needed.

Data source	Description
Remote sensing data	Data collected by satellites or other remote sensors that provide information on land, ocean, and atmospheric conditions (Kashtan Sundararaman et al., 2023)
Weather station data	Data collected from ground-based weather stations that measure temperature, humidity, pressure, wind speed, and other weather variables (Han et al., 2023)
Radar data	Data collected by radar systems that can detect precipitation, wind speed, and direction (Wang et al., 2023a)
Social media data	Data collected from social media platforms that can provide real-time information on natural disasters and their impacts (Platania et al., 2022)
Geospatial data	Data that includes information on terrain, land use, population density, and infrastructure (Stokes and Seto, 2019)

Current practices and tools

Historical data	Data from past natural disasters that can be used to train machine learning models for forecasting future events (Jiang et al., 2022)
Sensor data	Data collected by sensors deployed in disaster-prone areas that can measure seismic activity, water levels, and other variables (Wang et al., 2023b)
Mobile phone data	Data collected from mobile phone networks that can provide information on population movements and density during disasters (Yabe et al., 2022)

Figure 3. 'Types of data sources for natural hazard forecasting using machine learning algorithms' (Jain et al., 2023, p. 9).

Predictive analytics for humanitarian aid. A rapid review mapped predictive analytic initiatives in humanitarian aid, documenting 49 projects as well as secondary sources (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020). The review showed that predictive analytics were being used in the mitigation, preparedness and response phases of the humanitarian lifecycle, but not the recovery phase. Predictive analytics were also being used for functions such as human resource management, fundraising, and logistics. Analytics were most often used to identify where humanitarian crises would occur (71% of initiatives) and who would be affected (40%). Less frequently, they were used to predict what the affected situation would look like (26%) and when events would occur (18%). The most common applications were prediction of disease outbreak (9 initiatives), migration (9), conflict (7), disaster risk reduction (6), and food security (4). The initiatives covered in the review were primarily in Africa and the Arab world, with fewer applications in Asia and Latin America. Most initiatives used historical humanitarian data combined with ML and statistical modelling. Predictive analytics were used to complement rather than replace traditional analysis and forecasting. The most frequent users were large international agencies and small start-up companies. The review found little evidence of affected populations playing a significant role in the design or management of analytics in humanitarian work. Almost half the initiatives (23) claimed that predictive analytics would improve efficiency by saving time or money, although it was not possible to validate these claims. The review states that the ecosystem of humanitarian predictive analytics was not yet well defined or established. It noted that the Centre for Humanitarian Data¹⁰ was playing a key global convening role; sectoral and geographical specialists were also beginning to emerge. The use of predictive analytics was still an emerging practice, with pilot projects and innovations at an early stage, requiring further development and validation. It suggested that open data would be a significant enabler of predictive analytics in humanitarian action (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

Using NLP for humanitarian needs analysis and response. Rocca et al. (2023) discuss the use of NLP, suggesting it can be utilised to support evidence-based decision-making and facilitate operations. They give examples such as monitoring, predicting, and understanding crisis dynamics; enhancing communication with affected populations; and using unstructured text to generate structured datasets. NLP used for humanitarian purposes must satisfy high ethical standards, support low-resource languages, and be able to be used by non-experts in real-world contexts (Rocca et al., 2023). The authors give the example of the Data Entry and Exploration Platform (DEEP). DEEP was a collaborative platform which could be used to structure and categorise unstructured text data and apply analytical frameworks. It was possible to share text or create collections of data, annotate them manually or, with

¹⁰ <https://centre.humdata.org>

AI tools, analyse patterns and monitor trends (Rocca et al., 2023). As a practical example, DEEP facilitated secondary data analysis and the production of Humanitarian Needs Overviews in Afghanistan, Somalia, and South Sudan; it was used to support data analysis for planning for sudden onset emergencies in Mozambique and Pakistan; for complex emergencies in Libya, Nigeria, Yemen, and Ukraine; and in protracted crises such as civil unrest and population movement from Venezuela (Rocca et al., 2023). Platforms such as DEEP face persistent sustainability issues, including unstable funding streams and low use—with only 20% of registered users demonstrating active annual participation. IPIE’s report raised questions over DEEP’s ongoing sustainability, particularly since it was primarily funded by USAID (IPIE, 2025), and indeed it has been closed down.¹¹

AI applications in humanitarian healthcare. A review by Haykal et al. (2025) describes uses of AI in humanitarian work, for example, AI-driven telemedicine platforms that address demand for medical care in refugee camps; ML algorithms that identify patterns of disease and facilitate prediction and prevention of outbreaks; AI chatbots that provide health information in people’s native languages; AI counselling bots that offer psychological assistance to refugees and disaster survivors who suffer from trauma, stress, and anxiety in multiple languages; and AI-driven robots that can conduct basic medical assessments and deliver first-aid supplies. Haykal et al. (2025) summarise AI applications in humanitarian healthcare according to their purpose or description and ethical considerations, as shown in Figure 4.

Application name	Purpose/description	Ethical considerations
CIMA (Children immunization App)	Boosts vaccination adherence among refugee children	Informed consent, data privacy of children
Wysa	AI-powered mental health chatbot using CBT and mindfulness	Confidentiality, lack of human oversight
Woebot	AI chatbot for psychological support	Data protection, appropriateness in acute mental health crises
IBM Watson Health	Supports disease tracking and intervention (e.g., malaria control)	Bias in data sets, transparency of decision-making
ZzappMalaria	AI-powered app for identifying mosquito breeding sites to combat malaria	Location data sensitivity, equitable deployment
Google BERT	NLP tool for real-time translation in crisis communication	Risk of mistranslation, bias in language models
OpenAI Models	Used for NLP to enhance health communication and emergency alerts	Misinformation control, contextual sensitivity
MERON (by Kimetrica)	AI tool for rapid image-based malnutrition screening	Biometric data use, consent in vulnerable populations
Google Flood Forecasting Initiative	Predicts floods using real-time data and AI algorithms	Accuracy responsibility, access disparities

Figure 4. AI applications in humanitarian healthcare (Haykal, Goldust, Cartier, & Treacy, 2025, p. 02).

11 <https://www.thedeep.io>

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Search and rescue. Forms of AI in search and rescue (SAR) missions have been used since the 1990s (Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi, 2024). A timeline of the use of AI in SAR is provided in Figure 5, as appeared in Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi (2024).

Timeline of using artificial intelligence and technology in SAR missions

Figure 5. 'Timeline of using artificial intelligence and technology in SAR missions.' (Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi, 2024, p. 152014). FRID: radio-frequency identification; SAR: search and rescue; UAV: unmanned aerial vehicle; YOLO: You Only Look Once.

In recent years, there have been developments such as: "DronAID", a real-time drone system designed to detect people using passive infrared (PIR) sensors; a system that identifies people from unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) images using PIR and ultrasonic sensors; DL-aided wireless sensing systems for detecting people; ML and DL detection systems that use radar and Red-Green-Blue (RGB)/depth cameras; a drone-snowmobile technique that can scan broad areas to enable SAR teams to locate people more quickly; a downward-facing camera that can be installed on a drone to identify people and assess the safety of a possible landing place; an internet of drones (IoD) system with blockchain technology, edge servers, and UAVs to facilitate SAR; and the You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm, which is an open-source, real-time object detector, which simplifies the object detection task compared with other models designed for the same purpose (Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi, 2024).

Applications of ML within UAVs include: (1) enhancing the security and effectiveness of communication of information gathered by UAVs, such as by utilising a blockchain and ML-based structure called Block-USB which improves communication capabilities of UAVs within 6G networks; (2) improving network performance, for example, by using ANNs to improve the effectiveness of cooperative air and device-to-device (D2D) networks with UAVs; (3) the automated classification of geological characteristics; and (4) the distribution of online learning in swarms of UAVs, which involves autonomous training of ML models to collect and process data locally, which minimises the need for raw data sharing (Al-Allaq, Shakir, & Charafeddine, 2025).

In their review of literature on AI in SAR, Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) categorised technologies by the type of environment in which they can be used. The first type they considered was isolated wilderness areas, such as dense forests, mountains, deserts, coastal cliffs, and other terrains defined by

restricted access, expansive search areas, and difficult navigation. They found this was the most studied type of terrain in SAR technology research and suggested it was due to the availability of datasets for training and fewer regulations on flying UAVs. One of the technologies designed for such terrains was an AI detection system based on CNNs that used UAVs and multi-legged robots. The UAVs were designed to scan the area for initial detection and then robots would walk the area to confirm the presence of humans using voice detection. Another system used an interactive interface that connected UAVs and head-mounted display devices to create a mixed-reality environment to deal with issues such as poor identification in specific settings and real-time video streaming. Several studies identified by Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) implemented autonomous navigation for UAVs, which could be used, for example, to take images from closer distance, to scan specific areas, or to deliver immediate aid to a person.

In terms of marine SAR, which usually necessitates an immediate response from rescue teams, the literature identified by Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) described technologies such as a dynamic simulation model designed to optimise the setup of UAVs and human detection models in a marine environment; vision-based navigation and management of a joint unmanned surface vehicle (USV) and UAV system for marine SAR; Global Positioning System (GPS) and Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) modules to geolocate people; autonomous navigation systems for UAVs; and aid delivery systems.

Another type of environment described in the review by Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) was urban. Urban SAR usually involves individuals who become trapped, missing, or stranded because of disasters such as earthquakes, storms, and fires, for example, due to building collapse (Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi, 2024). Such operations often occur in densely populated areas and involve navigating through debris and structural hazards. The authors found that urban SAR technologies have been less studied in the literature than those for wilderness and marine SAR, possibly because there are fewer datasets available for training and more regulations on flying UAVs in urban areas. Nevertheless, they identified literature that describes technologies such as GPS modules to geolocate people; autonomous navigations systems for UAVs; and RGB cameras and thermal imaging to detect people (Bany Abdelnabi & Rabadi, 2024).

Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) outlined several challenges in using AI for SAR operations. One of the biggest is the availability of specialised datasets; to build accurate and efficient models, it is necessary to have training sets that are comprehensive, high-quality, and realistic. The authors comment that many of the available datasets are not based on real-life disasters or disaster-like scenarios, limiting their utility as training data. The lack of suitable training data results in limitations in model performance. There are many considerations for training data to be useful. For example, if bad weather and poor lighting were not featured in the training set, this may compromise the applicability of the model in such conditions. Some of the other considerations included the UAV's view angle, human postures, and the number of objects in the image. Bany Abdelnabi and Rabadi (2024) also warn that much of the current research is theoretical and many of the existing experiments were performed in a controlled environment, so more

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applied research is needed to understand factors such as wind speed, lighting, vibration, disruption, and bad weather, which can affect model performance, data transmission, and connectivity.

Location and deployment of goods and equipment. A systematic review by Farazmehr and Wu (2023) focused on the use of AI for locating and deploying essential goods and equipment during disasters. This review examined the use of AI within two broad sub-categories of disaster relief logistics: (1) creating a relief network (known as the *essential goods facility location problem (FLP)*) and (2) defining the operational pathways for aid distribution (known as the *vehicle routing problem (VRP)*). For FLP, AI can be used to select sites for stockpiling supplies in the event of disasters, for example, by considering the likelihood of disaster and the site's susceptibility, traffic movement and the formation of queues at the site, and any other relevant criteria. AI can also be applied to the VRP to facilitate the optimisation of distribution routes. For example, in urgent cold chain logistics, AI can be used to optimise routing and scheduling by considering potential destruction of the vehicle, the need for cooling, and the rate of goods degradation (Farazmehr & Wu, 2023).

Use of geographic information systems. Diehr et al. (2025) conducted a systematic review of 71 empirical studies on integrating AI and ML with GIS for disaster management and resilience. They identified six themes related to opportunities, shown in Figure 6. Many of the articles discussed disaster management and risk assessment, including real-time data collection, analysis and modelling, which could result in more accurate predictions and improved preparedness. Examples included using AI and ML to analyse satellite imagery, sensor readings, and social media feeds to identify patterns and trends that may signify potential disasters. The literature also highlighted the speed of AI and ML in facilitating early warnings and targeted interventions, for example, to mitigate weather-related disasters. Another practical application described is the use of AI-powered drones to create maps of vulnerable areas, to facilitate effective resource allocation. In post-disaster response, ML can use aerial imagery to facilitate needs assessment and resource allocation; media and social media analysis by AI can enable the identification of missing people and areas that require immediate attention. Real-time environmental monitoring and EWS were another topic covered by the literature identified. For example, integrating AI and GIS could enable analysis of real-time data from different sources, which could allow responders to improve the accuracy and timeliness of disaster responses (Diehr et al., 2025).

Figure 6. 'Themes emerging as opportunities for integrating GIS, AI, and ML in disaster management from the review.' (Diehr et al., 2025, p. 290).

The systematic review by Diehr et al. (2025) identified a number of challenges related to integrating GIS, AI, and ML in disaster management. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of challenges identified in the literature (Diehr et al., 2025). Computational and technical challenges were the most discussed theme. The literature described a need for high processing power and technical expertise to integrate GIS, AI, and ML. The need for significant data and computational resources means that in environments where such resources are limited, the potential for AI and ML models is reduced. A lack of technical expertise, such as skills in managing AI and ML models, processing large databases, and ensuring data compatibility and synchronisation can hinder GIS, AI, and ML integration (Diehr et al., 2025).

Figure 7. 'Themes emerging as challenges associated with integrating GIS, AI, and ML in disaster management from the review' (Diehr et al., 2025, p. 292).

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Collection of disaster loss data. A recent study examines current practices, challenges, and opportunities in disaster loss data collection and management across EU Member States and Participating States (EC JRC, 2025). A survey collected data from 23 institutions across 18 countries. The results show significant variation in institutional practices, such as legal frameworks, data collection methodologies, and hazard coverage. Some institutions reported advanced tools and legal structures, whilst others face challenges of resource constraints and fragmented responsibilities. Key findings from the study included the prevalence of data collection for river floods, flash floods, and storms, with limited coverage of technological hazards and the underutilisation of geospatial data. Looking to the future, the study highlights the need for standardisation of disaster loss data protocols, capacity enhancement, and establishing centralised platforms to improve data sharing and accessibility. The study's recommendations focus on the harmonisation of legal frameworks, the adoption of modern technologies, and fostering international collaboration (EC JRC, 2025).

Food security. The WFP's World Hunger Map¹² is a tool that provides near real-time monitoring of food insecurity in 94 countries. It uses ML-based predictive models to estimate the food security situation in areas that have insufficient data. The Map offers near real-time overviews of drivers of food insecurity such as climate hazards, conflict, vegetation coverage and rainfall. There are challenges, given that food security is highly contextual. ML models may struggle to capture complexities, and oversimplification of complex systems can lead to oversights or inaccurate predictions (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Migration. The Transhumance Tracking Tool¹³ collects data to identify transhumance movement and assess the risk of intercommunal conflict. AI-assisted remote sensing data can complement efforts, particularly where it is difficult or dangerous to access data. AI can play a role in identifying, assessing and even predicting migration. Research by the World Bank used ML to analyse data from over 442 million people from 189 different population censuses in 64 countries between 1960 and 2015. The model can classify variables, evaluate their importance in a range of migration scenarios, and generate forecasting models for future migration projections (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Climate. The World Bank's Climate Change Knowledge Portal¹⁴ offers visualised climate data, including historical and future climate trends at national and subnational scales. UNEP has developed the World Environment Situation Room¹⁵, which offers near real-time analysis and future predictions of environmental and climate hazards. AI is used in curating, aggregating, and visualising earth-observation data for the platform, including socio-economic and conflict-related variables. Other mapping tools include the Aqueduct Water Risk Atlas, Anomaly Hot Spots of Agricultural Production, and the Global Drought Observatory. UNEP's Strata¹⁶ platform can be used to visualise conflict and insecurity hotspots in climate change-exposed regions. When data are not available, modelled

12 <https://hungermap.wfp.org>

13 <https://migrationnetwork.un.org/practice/transhumance-tracking-tool-ttt>

14 <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org>

15 <https://wesr.unep.org>

16 <https://unepstrata.org>

probabilities of hazards are used. AI can help model hazard probabilities or process earth-observation data to fill data gaps (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Severe storms. The GAO report (US GAO, 2023) describes ProbSevere¹⁷, a ML model that has improved US forecasters' ability to issue warnings of severe thunderstorms and tornadoes. The Statistical Hurricane Intensity Prediction Scheme (SHIPS) uses a simple form of ML to predict rapid intensification more accurately. The relative rarity of certain disaster events, such as tornadoes, can make it difficult to collect ample data to train AI tools (Partnership for Public Service & Microsoft, 2020). An example of the successful implementation of AI is the ML algorithms used by the USA's National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration to forecast events such as hurricanes, blizzards, and heatwaves (Jain et al., 2023). For example, they use satellite data to predict a hurricane's track, intensity, and timing. In 2018, this technique was able to predict Hurricane Florence's path, which facilitated the response to it (Jain et al., 2023). The review by Haykal et al. (2025) describes the use of AI during Hurricane Harvey in 2017, when AI chatbots and automated response systems were implemented to coordinate emergency relief and direct people to shelters, food distribution centres, and medical aid stations.

Flooding. ML can provide flood predictions faster than traditional models, which makes them useful for flash floods. ML may also be able to analyse the causes of flooding, improving traditional models. A type of ML algorithm, Artificial Neural Networks, can deal with incomplete datasets. ML models may be able to incorporate data such as satellite and road camera images more efficiently than traditional models (US GAO, 2023). At the same time, ML maybe be unable to extrapolate to new situations (the 'generalisation problem' already mentioned). For example, some ML algorithms may perform well for short-term but not long-term predictions, or for lower but not higher flood volumes, or locations without prior flood data (US GAO, 2023). In managing floods, automated segmentation can facilitate the location and mapping of flood-affected areas as well as the assessment of flooding severity; CNNs can be used to recognise rising water levels; DL and ML approaches may help to identify and forecast floods, evaluate potential hazards, implement EWS, and analyse flood occurrences (Akhyar et al., 2024). The Dartmouth Flood Observatory uses ML algorithms to map and forecast floods with the help of satellite imagery; during the 2015 floods in Chennai, India, such flood maps were used for rescue and relief efforts (Jain et al., 2023).

Drought. A case study for managing agricultural drought and flood risks in the Lao People's Democratic Republic used AI to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of anticipatory triggering methodologies, enhancing the response. For drought management, the methodology combined six indicators that make up the Combined Drought Indicator (CDI), which successfully detected both severe and mild drought events. The approach has potential application beyond Laos and would need further testing and community engagement, as well as addressing the identified gaps (Isaev et al., 2024).

Wildfires. Applying ML to wildfire spread models is a promising research area. Significant computing power is needed during training; ML accuracy also requires domain expertise in wildfire research to ensure realistic modelling (US GAO, 2023). US GAO (2023) noted that training data are frequently

17 https://cimss.ssec.wisc.edu/severe_conv/

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unavailable for wildfires, but more recently, Ejaz and Choudhury (2025) summarised the available datasets for wildfire risk assessment and categorised them according to the sources of data, spatial coverage, temporal resolution, and data format. The list of datasets compiled by the authors is presented in Figure 8.

Cat.	Dataset	Source	Spatial coverage	Temporal resolution	Data format
R	MODIS Fire Products (Justice et al., 2002)	NASA	Global	4x daily	CSV, Shapefile, KML
R	Landsat Imagery (Lovel and Dwyer, 2012)	USGS	Global	16-day revisit	GeoTIFF
R	VIIRS Active Fire Data (Schroeder et al., 2014)	NASA/NOAA	Global	2x daily	CSV, Shapefile, KML
R	Sentinel-2 Imagery (Drusch et al., 2012)	ESA	Global	5-day revisit	JPEG2000, GeoTIFF
R	LANDFIRE (Zahn, 2015)	USDI	Continental US, Alaska, Hawaii	Updated every 2-3 years (From 2001)	GeoTIFF, IMG
R	Copernicus Global Land Service (Buchhorn et al., 2020)	Copernicus	Global	Monthly	GeoTIFF, NetCDF
R	FIRMS (Anon, 2024a)	NASA/NOAA	Global	Near real-time	CSV, Shapefile
I	RAWS (Anon, 2024c)	USDA Forest Service	Continental US	Hourly/Daily	CSV, NetCDF
I	GRIDMET (Anon, 2024b)	University of Idaho	Continental US	Daily, 4km resolution	NetCDF
	NFDRS (Anon, 2025)	USFS	Continental US	Daily	XML, JSON
I	FWI System (Canada, 2024)	Canadian Forest Service	Global	Daily	CSV, Raster
G	NLCD (U.S. Geological Survey, 2024)	USGS	Continental US	Every 5 years	GeoTIFF, Shapefile
G	MTBS (MTBS Program, 2024)	USGS	Continental US	Annual updates (From 1984)	Shapefile, GeoTIFF, CSV
G	OpenStreetMap (contributors, 2024)	OSM Community	Global	Continuously updated	GeoJSON, XML, Shapefile
G	Global Forest Change (Hansen Dataset) (Hansen et al., 2013)	University of Maryland	Global	Annual (2000-2022)	GeoTIFF, CSV
H	NIFC Database (National Interagency Fire Center, 2024)	NIFC	Continental US	Annual	CSV, Database
H	State Wildfire Records	State Forestry Departments	Individual US States	Annual/Historical	Various (CSV, Excel)
H	GFED (Global Fire Emissions Database (GFED), 2024)	NASA	Global	Monthly	NetCDF, CSV
H	ICS-209 Incident Reports (St. Denis et al., 2023)	USFS	Continental US	Incident-based	CSV, XML

Figure 8. 'Primary Datasets and Details for Wildfire Risk Assessment' (Ejaz & Choudhury, 2025, p. 5).
Remote Sensing=R, In-Situ Data= I, Geospatial Data= G, Historical Data= H

In forest fire management, recent advances include the development of DL segmentation algorithms capable of recognising and analysing patterns and characteristics of forest fires in satellite or aerial photos, and DL and ML approaches that can improve early detection, prediction accuracy, and resource allocation efficiency (Akhyar et al., 2024). The ML pipeline for the risk assessment of wildfires, presented in Figure 9, typically consists of the following stages: data acquisition, pre-processing, feature extraction, model training, and post-processing (Ejaz & Choudhury, 2025). ML models can be trained to predict wildfire risk, based on approaches tailored to the relevant data and prediction task.

Figure 9. 'Machine learning pipeline for wildfire risk assessment' (Ejaz & Choudhury, 2025, p. 4).

A recent example of what works when applying AI to wildfire response was given in the review by Haykal et al. (2025), who described AI applications during the Los Angeles wildfires, including predictive modelling to assess fire trajectories, optimise evacuation routes, and facilitate effective deployment of medical teams.

Earthquakes. One of the tasks that AI can perform is semantic segmentation, during which class labels are assigned to image pixels to help computers understand visual information (IBM, n.d.). In earthquake management, segmentation algorithms can use satellite or aerial imagery to identify and delineate seismically active zones (Akhyar et al., 2024). Additionally, CNNs, which are a type of ML that can be used for image classification and object recognition tasks, can be trained to assess disaster severity and create maps of the affected regions; DL and ML methods can be used to improve earthquake detection, prediction, EWS, structural damage assessment, and post-event analysis (Akhyar et al., 2024). An ML algorithm developed at the Earthquake Research Institute at the University of Tokyo can predict earthquakes up to 10 seconds in advance by analysing seismic data and have an accuracy rate of 90% when it comes to earthquakes of magnitude ≥ 3 (Jain et al., 2023). After the 2023 Türkiye-Syria earthquake, AI was used to predict aftershocks, which helped rescue teams to plan operations. AI-assisted robots were used to navigate rubble and search for survivors, and AI-driven tools were used to

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analyse data from social media and satellites to identify areas that had not yet received aid (Haykal et al., 2025).

Public-private cooperation for natural hazards and early-warning. In 2022, the ESCAP developed a methodology and capacity-building modules for flood inundation mapping and hotspot analysis, using temporal active (Synthetic Aperture Radar) and passive (optical) satellite images in Google Earth Engine cloud computing (ESCAP, 2023). Google AI for Social Good is an example of private and public cooperation to scale up access to and availability of EWS. Google's flood early-warning service started in Bangladesh in 2018. A forecasting model can allow for doubling of the lead time for many alerts, as well as providing information about flood depth, when and how much flood waters are likely to rise. The information is provided through mobile phones in different formats and local languages. By 2021, Google had expanded its coverage to 360 million people in India and Bangladesh, resulting in over 115 million alerts. Over time, it was able to scale up its flood forecasting services to cover more than 90 countries. Google has created a multi-hazard EWS for natural hazards, covering various types of disasters, including wildfires and hurricanes. It provides real-time safety information and alerts to communities at risk. For wildfires, infrared and optical imagery is used to identify 'hot spots' and provide real-time safety information. Google's earthquake EWS utilises Android phones as 'mini-seismometers' to detect earthquakes, aggregating accelerometer sensor data from phones. For hurricanes, Google Maps provides crisis notification cards and up-to-date road conditions for safe navigation (cited in ESCAP, 2023).

International initiatives. The *WMO Unified Data Policy*¹⁸ recognises the need for robust data governance, based on the principles of free and unrestricted data exchange. It provides a framework to harness the developments in AI/ML for weather and climate prediction (WMO, 2024). UN Global Pulse¹⁹ focuses on the use of big data in development, humanitarian aid, and the peacebuilding sectors (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

The International Charter: Space and Major Disasters²⁰ is a worldwide collaboration, where satellite data is made available for disaster management and risk reduction insight. It provides a single access point that operates 24/7, at no cost to the user. Other initiatives include the International Working Group on Satellite-based Emergency Mapping, the Committee on Earth-observation Satellites (CEOS), UN-SPIDER (a United Nations space-related programme), Europe's Copernicus, and the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (Pellegrino, Sen & Angeletti, 2021). The ITU, WMO and UNEP established the Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence for Natural Disaster Management (FG-AI4NDM)²¹ in December 2020.

The Disaster Connectivity Map is an initiative by the ITU and the Emergency Telecommunications Cluster (ETC), assisted by the GSMA Mobile for Humanitarian Innovation programme. It helps first responders by showing information on a map, such as an overview of the physical network infrastructure, mobile

18 <https://wmo.int/wmo-unified-data-policy-resolution-res1>

19 <https://www.unglobalpulse.org>

20 <https://www.un-spider.org/international-charter-space-and-major-disasters>

21 <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4ndm/Pages/default.aspx>

network coverage and connectivity performance (ITU, ETC, GSMA, 2024 cited in OECD, 2025a). These maps aggregate data from multiple sources to provide near real-time network coverage and performance.

Advanced systems like Data Insights for Social and Humanitarian Action (DISHA) now integrate satellite imagery, drone footage, phone data, and crowdsourced reports for humanitarian response. DISHA is led by the UN Global Pulse in partnership with numerous agencies including UNOSAT, the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), the World Food Program, and [Google.org](https://www.google.org). The system is being tested, and a comparison was conducted across nine disaster situations to examine how AI analysis would perform compared to more manual assessments. The early results are promising, showing that damage assessments could be potentially reduced by 'a time factor of six', while also expanding the range of assessments (IPIE, 2025).

Public warning systems. The EU-ALERT system is an example of standards for public warning systems based on call broadcast technology (ETSI, cited in OECD, 2025a).

Social media. A workshop run by the JRC (Lorini et al., 2024) explored the role of social media in enhancing DRM practices. Practical examples included two-way weather risk communication in Canada, using both ML trained and untrained approaches. In 2020, a UNESCO project, *Strengthening disaster prevention approaches in Eastern Africa*, developed an AI-supported chatbot with the private sector to enable citizens to share critical information before, during and after life-threatening natural events. Together with the company Citibeats, UNESCO collected data between 2018 and 2021 from social media and other media sources in Eastern Africa. The data were then categorised using NLP and AI. The report suggests that combining qualitative and quantitative insight can give greater insight into citizens' concerns and identify possible areas of action (Citibeats & UNESCO, 2021).

Artificial Intelligence for Digital Response (AIDR)²² is open-source software that collects and categorises tweets posted during humanitarian crises. The private sector has cooperated in developing a real-time visualisation platform using AI, NLP, and an application programming interface (API) to process data from various sources, including social media networks. Such a platform could enable humanitarian organisations to benefit from visualised real-time information on the severity of disasters, hospital locations, and weather reports (Kim & Boulanin, 2023)

Participatory approaches and collective crisis intelligence. UN country teams in Libya and Yemen conducted public consultations assisted by AI that involved 1,000 participants from multiple locations in a single session. Input from AI-facilitated consultations can serve as part of a diverse set of information sources (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). A project between Nesta's Centre for Collective Intelligence Design (CCID) and Data Analytics Practice (DAP), the Nepal Red Cross and Cameroon Red Cross, IFRC Solferino Academy, and Newcastle University's Open Lab was carried out between April 2021 and May 2022. It developed and evaluated early prototypes of two collective crisis intelligence tools. These were: (1) *NFRI-Predict1*, a tool that predicted which non-food aid items were most needed by different types of households in regions of Nepal, following a crisis; and (2) Report and Respond, a French language

22 <https://aidr.qcri.org/>

What works and emerging challenges

SMS-based tool that allowed Red Cross volunteers in Cameroon to check the accuracy of COVID-19 information they heard from the community and receive real-time guidance on appropriate responses. The project found that collective crisis intelligence can make humanitarian action timelier and more appropriate to local needs. It was able to show that collective crisis intelligence and participatory AI can help increase trust in AI tools, although more research is needed to determine why this is. It suggests that few AI tools take specific local problems faced by frontline workers as their starting point, even though it is important for their uptake. The main challenges found included the lack of existing good quality data, adequate technical infrastructure, skills and data literacy in local organisations. It was also challenging to change existing ways of working towards more active 'co-design'; it took longer for teams to understand each other and establish effective, multi-disciplinary ways of working. The report flags the limited toolbox for participatory AI, making it difficult to design activities that are appropriate and effective. Future R&D would need to focus on developing AI methods that can function with sparse or low-quality datasets, alongside digital tools that can work in situations where there are limited resources. Greater coordination is required to fill data gaps and help organisations document existing AI models and datasets. Increased investment in technical and community participation skills is needed, together with further experimentation and codification of participatory AI methods to support their more widespread adoption (Berditchevskaia, Peach & Stewart, 2022).

What works and emerging challenges

The following section gives examples from the literature to address the questions posed.

Benchmarking of weather models. The *United in Science* report (WMO, 2024) describes how the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) has evaluated AI weather models trained on ERA5. This combines observational data with models to provide frequent updates on atmospheric conditions. Predictions of severe weather events like windstorms, extreme temperatures, and tropical cyclones were analysed; the results showed that current ML models consistently performed well, but with some limitations. For example, ML models could forecast accurately the path of tropical storms but may underestimate storm intensity. They could predict intense windstorms but may underestimate maximum wind speeds. AI forecasts from ECMWF's 9-km resolution forecasts could capture patterns of summer and winter temperatures but may not capture extremes accurately, in particular the lowest observed temperatures. Comparisons against standard benchmarks showed that AI forecasts from ECMWF's operational 9-km analysis were generally more accurate than global forecasts produced using a traditional method. However, the report notes that errors in AI forecasts and traditional physics-based model forecasts are often correlated, which highlights shared challenges in predicting certain weather situations (WMO, 2024).

Limited data quality and availability remain a significant challenge. This includes the scale of data required for training, uneven data availability, and gaps in data for weather modelling. Training then relies on model outputs or direct observations, which is more difficult and computationally expensive. A lack of transparency and unequal access to data and/or limitations in user skillsets reduce the uptake and effectiveness of AI/ML weather models (WMO, 2024).

Limitations of predictive models. It is far easier to make reliable predictions in slow-onset disasters like droughts than for rapid onset disasters like earthquakes. An assumption made is that the future will be like the past, but predictive models may not be very good at detecting where there is change. The more time that has passed since an update, the less accurate models are at prediction. Predictive models find patterns or correlations, but not necessarily why something happens (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

Data analysis. A review of Management Responses to 160 humanitarian-focused UNICEF evaluations for 2017–2024 was conducted (UNICEF, 2024). Generative AI was helpful in identifying key themes for further inquiry and analysis, but only human researchers could answer the research questions. AI struggled with identifying trends over time, dealing with anomalies in the data, and grasping nuance. Although AI was useful in reviewing large number of documents to identify themes, traditional methods of qualitative coding and manual analysis enabled greater specificity in understanding the themes and what they meant for UNICEF. In conclusion, AI users were advised to treat it like a ‘research assistant’, alongside a human with the necessary skills and expertise, who could verify, review and validate all preliminary results. The study suggests that prompt engineering is needed to get good answers from AI, requiring practice to obtain adequate answers from AI chatbots. It was noted that generative AI can also be poor at numerical counting and at understanding nuance (UNICEF, 2024).

Training and user uptake. Many organisations may lack the training and technical capacity to use advanced tools. It would therefore be important to make dashboards and mapping tools more user-friendly and accessible. At the same time, there are risks associated with the use of dashboards; such tools may be under-used by policy actors. The challenge is to understand how information can be accessed by a range of users, how it can reach policymakers, and how policy interventions can be supported by information that is more accurate and up-to-date. Communication and training activities can help target end users (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

The GAO lists a number of challenges to be addressed in the US (but may apply more widely):

- 1. Communication between end users and developers.** More interaction between user and developer can determine what features are important and whether ML is needed to obtain the sort of information required.
- 2. Interdisciplinary collaboration.** Collaborating across different disciplines can be challenging.
- 3. Competing objectives within organisations.** Competing objectives may lead to missed opportunities for data sharing and greater collaboration.
- 4. Funding and technology transfer.** The effectiveness of the process to get from research to operational implementation can be variable.

Evidence gaps and future opportunities

- 5. Workforce and resource needs** can create barriers to the uptake of ML. There may be knowledge gaps, including
- a. *Lack of domain expertise.* Some companies may be developing ML models without domain expertise.
 - b. *Educational requirements.* Universities and the government could do more to prepare the workforce by training them with ML-related skills. There are insufficient professional developmental opportunities in ML.
 - c. *Pay scales.* Government salary limitations and workforce location requirements makes it difficult to compete with other sectors.
 - d. *High costs for training ML models.* Some ML technologies, such as emulators, require extensive computational resources for training.
 - e. *Computational resources for running ML models.* Using ML models can incur significant up-front computing costs that can be prohibitive or strain computing infrastructure.

Use of social media and participatory methods. A project between the Swinburne node of the ARC Centre of Excellence for Automated Decision-Making and Society (ADM+S) and the Australian Red Cross created an open platform to enable the mapping of community resources for disaster preparedness. Building collaboration involved the following steps: (1) identifying datasets that are useful in representing local community assets (people, groups, services, infrastructure, local knowledge, events and activities); (2) establishing the means to prepare data, analytics and visualisation that are responsible, ethical and inclusive; (3) exploring and testing the feasibility of an open platform and dashboard; (4) conducting usability testing. The study suggests that technologies and tools for disaster response that are community-centred and inclusive can result in greater community investment. Working with data at community level also involves building trust, local knowledge and capability (McCosker, Shaw, Calyx, Kang & Albury, 2022).

Dependencies. So-called ‘techno-colonialism’ could lead to dependency and inequality across the world (IMPACT, 2023). Concerns around ‘regulatory colonialism’ and ‘data imperialism’—where globally dominant regulatory frameworks set de-facto global standards— may be an issue (Paillé et al., 2024). Countering ‘techno-solutionism’ means that humanitarian solutions should be needs-based, and not solely technology-based (IMPACT, 2023). Geopolitical polarisation may impact access to critical and emerging technologies and the setting of technological standards, given competition between states and blocs (Kamberaj et al., 2024).

Evidence gaps and future opportunities

A rapid evidence review identified developments in humanitarian research over the ten years, from 2014 to 2024 (Kelly, 2024). It found an increasing amount of humanitarian data and open-source data

across the sector, but questions over its effective use. Examples of areas for further research included: (1) identifying end-user system requirements against actual data and analytical capabilities; (2) examining the ethics of AI deployment in disaster management environments; (3) considering current workforce arrangements, including skills and training; (4) ensuring decision-making tools are accessible and inclusive (Natural Hazards Research Australia, 2024).

Greater support is needed to provide the necessary data, tools and packages to assist with AI development, together with increased understanding of models, applications for AI-based methods, and the development of standards and internationally recognised guidelines. Open-source data, developing AI tools, and advancing AI-related research are all areas of opportunity (ESCAP, 2023). Digital infrastructure, training and capacity building, access to funding, and effective data governance frameworks are all important, as are education, public awareness, and building public trust (WMO, 2024).

According to the WMO's report (2024) on weather forecasting, the future may bring foundation models that are more robust; these can be trained on large, varied datasets and without a specific task in mind, enabling them to be adapted to more specific applications. Existing atmospheric AI/ML models could be extended to encompass the full Earth system, improving climate prediction as well as weather forecasting. Incorporating data from commercial satellites as well as crowd-sourced data could enhance the performance of AI/ML models. Providing low-cost federated data storage platforms and computing infrastructure, in combination with standardised tools, could help democratise the use and exploitation of ML worldwide (WMO, 2024).

It is important to pool data and incentivise data sharing, as well as addressing data continuity and the availability of more granular data (Muench et al., 2024). Data interoperability is important to integrating data from different sources into existing systems, tools and platforms (OCHA, 2021).

Global governance and frameworks should be accessible to all. Enhanced transparency in AI/ML weather models, with greater openness and traceability of training data, are important, together with addressing systemic biases. Training and capacity development are needed (WMO, 2024). A council or agency with stakeholder representation could be established at national level, allowing for the successful adoption of AI by disaster management agencies. It could be tasked with the development of policies, guidelines, and codes of conduct for the adoption of AI in the disaster sector (ESCAP, 2022).

SIPRI cites the example of the Water, Peace and Security partnership²³, where there is limited evidence on how its analytic insights have fed into decision-making processes. It is unclear whether this is due to the complexity of the decision-making process or to distrust of AI within decision-support tools. It suggests that more transparency and accessibility would help policymakers make use of insights from crisis EWS (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Emerging new technologies. Researchers are looking into multimodal AI, which can process information from different modalities, including images, raw data, videos, and text (Ellenweig et al.,

23 <https://waterpeacesecurity.org>

Evidence gaps and future opportunities

2024). A new set of technologies involving digital twins and the metaverse is emerging. Digital twins are a virtual representation that reflect accurately a physical object or system. The metaverse is an ecosystem of virtual worlds that provides immersive experiences. Efforts so far have focused around creating interactive simulations to educate users. For example, Malaysia studied flood preparedness among higher education students using a metaverse environment (cited in WMO, 2024). The future is likely to see the integration of multiple technologies (WMO, 2024). The European Commission has launched the Destination Earth²⁴ initiative, with some of the first identified digital twins and use cases being DRR oriented (WEF, 2024).

A report by ESCAP (2022) used the horizon scanning method to assess the possible benefits and challenges of employing geospatial artificial intelligence (GeoAI) technology; it was based on a literature review, opinions from experts and a review of reports. GeoAI is an emerging framework that combines innovations in geospatial technology, together with methods in AI and big data. It is playing an increasingly important role in DRR, from the forecasting of extreme events and the development of hazard maps to the detection of events in real-time, the provision of situational awareness and decision support.

Agentic AI. One of the trends of AI is the growth of AI agents, which can be tasked with doing research, completing tasks, and carrying out actions on behalf of an individual or organization. If reliability of output improves, these agents could make use of datasets, in addition to social media, news, and other channels to perform real-time semantic analysis, provide more accurate alerts and potentially even policy recommendations (IPIE, 2025).

IT and infrastructure resilience. Countries are starting to adapt ITU guidelines for the development and implementation of National Emergency Telecommunication Plans and other tailored contingency plans. The private sector offers an efficient and low-cost way to provide high-speed Internet connectivity. At a global level, the Common Alerting Protocol will be an element of standardised EWS. At a local level, identifying early actions that are applicable for multiple hazards will lower the learning and uptake curve for community-based and owned EWS. A robust IT infrastructure and information governance approach must be established and maintained (ESCAP, 2023). Infrastructure resilience is vital. For example, advanced monitoring systems within infrastructure management (such as sensors) can improve the response and ability to pre-empt potential failures (Natural Hazards Research Australia, 2024). Investment is needed in infrastructure enhancement and improved network resilience. Satellite networks can provide critical backup connectivity and upgrading mobile broadband services is essential for sharing real-time data with emergency services (OECD, 2025a).

Personalisation. Emergency warnings could become more personalised, by making use of data generated by an individual's digital footprint. This could lead to the creation of personal digital twins that mirror an individual's physical, psychological, and behavioural characteristics. These twins could then generate alerts that are geographically specific and tailored to individual circumstances, behaviours, vulnerabilities and preferences. Chatbots and virtual assistants could ask questions specific

²⁴ <https://destination-earth.eu>

to someone's circumstances, providing real-time updates and advice. Augmented reality could enable people to see and understand the potential outcomes of emergency warnings; AI could highlight at-risk areas and preparation activities. At the same time, personalised warnings raise important considerations, such as privacy, data security, and the need for opt-in and opt-out mechanisms. Ensuring equitable access to these systems is crucial and back-up systems will still be required. A global emergency warning system application could enable tourists to receive warnings about emergencies, in a language and format that is easy for them to understand. The global system would need to be integrated with local and national systems, requiring cooperation and data sharing agreements between countries, as well as standardised formats for issuing warnings (Natural Hazards Research Australia, 2024).

Crowdsourcing and citizen science. Crowdsourcing platforms enable citizens to report real-time information on hazards, such as flooding, earthquakes, or wildfires, directly from the affected areas. Citizen science engages local communities in gathering data related to risk, such as environmental conditions, infrastructure vulnerabilities, and community resilience. Such initiatives can generate valuable datasets and foster a sense of empowerment and ownership. A bottom-up approach can help build trust, collaboration, and resilience-building within communities (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction & CIMA, 2024).

Skillsets and uptake. It is crucial that enough AI specialists are educated, trained, and retained so as to ensure the development, maintenance, and deployment of AI in civil protection (Kamberaj et al., 2024). An understanding of workforce capability could identify the skills and resources required (Natural Hazards Research Australia, 2024). AI tool creators and users need to educate emergency professionals about the benefits of such tools and explain how they can help, encouraging their use and conducting impact assessment. Emergency responders must often make quick decisions, so any AI tool for disaster resilience should be designed for the unique nature of the job and the environment in which it operates (Partnership for Public Services & Microsoft, 2020).

OCHA surveyed thousands of humanitarian professionals in 2019 and found that big data, predictive analytics, and statistical modelling were the top three areas that humanitarian workers wanted to learn more about. This led the Centre to begin a workstream dedicated to predictive analytics (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

A literature review (IMPACT, 2023) found information gaps that would merit further exploration and investigation. Firstly, there is a need to study lessons learned from actual implementation of AI and ML tools in humanitarian settings. This includes a comprehensive understanding and assessment of their performance in real-world situations, with the identification and mitigation of biases that may arise during deployment. Another is ethical risk management, which includes addressing ethical challenges and dilemmas that emerge, such as data privacy, algorithmic fairness and transparency, along with the potential consequences of automated decision-making processes (IMPACT, 2023).

AI recommendations for DRM

The overall aim should be to overcome legal and ethical challenges, whilst at the same time promoting innovation and investment in AI (Kamberaj et al., 2024). Recommendations to policymakers in the IPIE report (2025) focus on (1) incorporating human rights and ‘do no harm’ principles at every stage of AI design and deployment; (2) funding evidence-based initiatives and publishing data on successes and failures; (3) supporting smaller, locally relevant language models that reflect diversity; (4) promoting transparency and accountability for AI tools; (5) building stakeholder partnerships across relevant sectors.

The literature also points to:

Deeper understanding of AI in a policy context. Policymakers should be able to understand and contextualise AI-generated insights, taking into account the implications of different thresholds for policy interventions, alongside associated risks of action or inaction (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Modelling. Policymakers could consider the following options to help address challenges related to the development, implementation, and use of ML for natural hazard modelling:

1. *Data collection, sharing, and use.* Expand data collection efforts, improve existing datasets, and facilitate data sharing. Potential downsides could include cost, risks in data security and constraints resulting from imposing data standards.
2. *ML education and training.* Foster ML expertise within academia and government. This may require substantial investment in training.
3. *Recruitment and retention and certain resource shortfalls.* Provide workforce incentives and invest in public-private partnerships. Potential challenges include costs and risks associated with private-public partnerships.
4. *Bias mitigation and trust in data and ML models.* Potential considerations include costs and slowing the speed of development (US GAO, 2023).

Cooperation between stakeholders. Cooperation between governments, researchers, and policy actors could contribute to more comprehensive and accurate data (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Infrastructure, digital literacy, disinformation. Access to digital infrastructure and digital literacy are important policy considerations (Kim & Boulanin, 2023). An improved approach to content monitoring and preventing hate speech and disinformation could involve: 1) more investment in AI tools that counter disinformation; 2) protection and training for workers responsible for monitoring content; 3) increased investment in multilingual moderation, especially in conflict-prone or fragile settings; 4) consideration of disinformation in training data, and 5) more transparent data sharing with researchers and other stakeholders (Fournier-Tombs et al., 2023).

Data analytics. More open data could be published to extend the potential for predictive analytics. To protect vulnerable populations from harm, humanitarian agencies should apply the precautionary principle in data collection and sharing. Affected populations also need to be involved. Funding should be linked to risk assessment, mitigation and knowledge sharing on the ethics and potential challenges of predictive analytics. Funders could support the development of geographical or thematic specialisms, knowledge-sharing activities and ethical guidelines for practice (Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

Humans in the loop. The Centre for Humanitarian Data reminds practitioners of the value of keeping ‘humans in the loop’ and cautions that predictive analytic models should be seen as tools rather than solutions, requiring the involvement of human decision-makers from the beginning (cited in Hernandez & Roberts, 2020).

Social media. Recommendations on social media data for researchers and practitioners are to: (1) develop pilot projects to test the integration of social media data into existing emergency response frameworks; (2) refine guidelines and protocols for social media use; (3) collaborate with EU Member States to explore the development of national strategies that incorporate new tools and methodologies (Lorini et al., 2024). Recommendations for policymakers and practitioners are to: (1) assess disaster response frameworks to identify where social media tools can be integrated; (2) establish training modules on the use of social media in disaster contexts; (3) implement pilot projects to test the effectiveness of social media integration and refine approaches, based on real-world data; (4) engage with relevant stakeholders to ensure a balanced approach to social media use in emergencies; (5) monitor the effectiveness of social media tools and adjust strategies, based on feedback and new technological developments (Lorini et al., 2024).

Pro-social approaches. Collaboration with technology designers is starting to embed values like empathy, mutual understanding, and trust-building into digital infrastructures. Early pilots suggest that pro-social algorithms can increase exposure to diverse perspectives and reduce harmful misinformation. At the same time, AI should not be regarded as a substitute for human connection (IPIE, 2025).

Ethical AI development. Policymakers should ensure that AI is embedded in frameworks that prioritise justice, equity and inclusion. Recommendations for ensuring inclusive and ethical AI development include: (1) prioritising fundamental human rights; (2) funding applied practices that document effective and ineffective strategies; (3) fostering cross-sectoral collaboration; (4) supporting the development of smaller language models; (5) developing policy and ethical guidance that is rooted in human rights, to promote ethical AI use (IPIE, 2025).

International support and brokerage. International organisations can support or coordinate the production and distribution of AI-generated insights, as well as contributing to the quality of AI outputs. Stakeholders from countries particularly affected by climate-related security risks should have a critical role in the development of AI systems (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

AI recommendations for DRM

Participatory methods. Working closely with affected communities for more participatory design approaches could help identify areas where technologies could effectively support response and recovery efforts (IMPACT, 2023).

Recommendations for policymakers in the area of climate security (but could be applied more widely) include support for: (1) inclusive access to digital infrastructure and capacity building; (2) the development of an open-access AI tool for data collection in conflict-affected and fragile countries; (3) critical research on AI and climate security (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Recommendations for researchers in the area of climate security (but could be applied more widely) include the following. First, to conduct empirical research and explore methodological solutions to explore the potential and limitations of AI. This could include case studies and papers that discuss methodological issues and generate actionable policy insights or novel methodologies and empirical techniques. Second is to consider the ethical and political risks associated with the use of AI methods. This should include responsible data sharing, conducting risk assessments and mitigation to protect privacy and fundamental rights of individuals. Third is to maintain close links with affected communities in the development of AI tools (Kim & Boulanin, 2023).

Recommended policy measures on network resilience can include infrastructure enhancement, including deployment of redundant infrastructure and technological upgrades (OECD, 2025a).

Recommendations on CBRN. It is important to invest in AI-based monitoring systems for the early detection and real-time response to CBRN attacks. An ethics committee should be instated to oversee technologies relevant to CBRN materials and threats. Governments should ensure that the materials and technologies required to create CBRN threats are well monitored (Ajaykumar, 2024).

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Annex: Literature review methods

The initial literature search was conducted in May 2025, based on the scoping questions in a draft Concept Note. The draft narrative was completed in July 2025 and circulated to DG ECHO, the SAM Secretariat and the SAPEA Working Group. It underwent an iterative process of revision, in response to feedback. It was updated with new literature in October 2025. The final draft was completed in November 2025 and underwent a plagiarism check. The final version was published in December 2025.

For this review, both academic and grey (e.g. major organisational reports) literature was searched, along with reference works for definitions. Academic literature was limited to existing reviews, with systematic reviews prioritised where possible. The Scopus and Web of Science databases were searched, and results were exported and deduplicated, after which they were screened for relevance. The most relevant publications were selected for inclusion in this review and summarised. The grey literature and policy database Overton was searched for grey literature. Reports that appeared relevant were downloaded and reviewed and if appropriate, retained and summarised.

The sources searched to identify literature for this review, along with the search queries, are detailed in Table S1.

Source	Search date	Search query	Number of	Comments
Overton	21/05/2025	"Civil protection" Humanitarian "emergency response" "disaster response" OR "disaster management" and (AI OR "artificial intelligence")	49	Relevant results were downloaded for further review
Scopus	27/05/2025	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (ai OR "artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "large language model*" OR llm)) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY ((emergenc* W/2 (prepar* OR anticipat*)) OR ("disaster risk management") OR ((crisis OR crises OR disaster*) W/2 respon*) OR ("decision making" W/3 (crisis OR crises OR emergenc* OR disaster*)))) AND PUBYEAR > 2022 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re"))	66	All results were exported and deduplicated against the WoS search (below)

Annex: Literature review methods

Web of Science	27/05/2025	1 TS=(ai OR "artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "large language model*" OR llm) 2 TS=((emergenc* NEAR/2 (prepar* OR anticipat*)) OR ("disaster risk management") OR ((crisis OR crises OR disaster*) NEAR/2 respon*) OR ("decision making" NEAR/3 (crisis OR crises OR emergenc* OR disaster*))) 3 #1 AND #2 4 #1 AND #2 Timespan: 2023-01-01 to 2025-12-31 (Publication Date) 5 #1 AND #2 Timespan: 2023-01-01 to 2025-12-31 (Publication Date) Document Types: Review Article	54	All results were exported and deduplicated against the Scopus search (above), resulting in 76 unique records
Oxford Handbooks	21/07/2025	"artificial intelligence" AND (overview OR introduction OR definitions) AFTER year 2020	1	Downloaded for use in the introduction
LibSearch	21/07/2025	"artificial intelligence" OR AI AND (overview OR introduction OR definitions) AFTER year 2020	1	Downloaded for use in the introduction
Scopus	09/10/2025	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (ai OR "artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "large language model*" OR llm)) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY ((emergenc* W/2 (prepar* OR anticipat*)) OR ("disaster risk management") OR ((crisis OR crises OR disaster*) W/2 respon*) OR ("decision making" W/3 (crisis OR crises OR emergenc* OR disaster*)))) AND PUBYEAR > 2024 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re"))	45	An update of the original search from May. All downloaded and deduplicated against the original search and the updated WoS search, resulting in a total of 104 unique articles.
Web of Science	09/10/2025	1: TS=(ai OR "artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "large language model*" OR llm)	23	An update of the original search from May. All downloaded and deduplicated against the original search and the updated Scopus search, resulting in a total of 104 unique articles.
Overton	17/10/2025	crisis management" OR "crisis risk" OR "crisis response" OR "disaster management" OR "disaster response" OR "disaster risk") AND (AI OR "artificial intelligence"). Last 2 years (2024/2025)	21	Downloaded for further review

Table S1. Search audit.

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